

WORK LIFE BALANCE: THE KEY DRIVER OF EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Our changing economy and the attitude of workforce can join together to create the work environment where competent employees who are distressed in their current situations are motivated to find a new place to “hang their hats.” Work-life balance is key driver of employee’s satisfaction. A highly involved workforce is 50% more productive than a distressed workforce. The majority of HR professionals (80%) feel employee involvement is important or extremely important to business success. Employee involvement has emerged as a critical driver of business success in today’s competitive marketplace. Employee involvement is increasingly viewed as a “win-win” strategy for companies, employees, and their communities alike. In addition, work/life balance is increasingly important for involvement and affects retention. This paper will examine some of the literature on Employee involvement, explore work-place culture & work-life balance policies & practices followed in industries in order to promote employee involvement in their organizations to increase their employee’s productivity and retain them.

INTRODUCTION

There are many dimensions to a full life, including our inner lives, our families, our work, our community, and our spirituality. As professionals, we face competing demands, and by necessity, make difficult choices each day. Many clinicians feel a lack of balance between work and the rest of their lives, which can lead to discontent, guilt, and chronic stress. We may prioritize our work and our families, and neglect our own physical, emotional, and spiritual health. It may lead to low productivity, absenteeism, employee turnover. Employee involvement has emerged as a critical driver of business success in today’s competitive market place. The employee involvement is a way of engaging employees at all level in the thinking process of an organization.

Employee Involvement creates the environment for the employees to go long or extra mile in their career’ - can have a very strong effect on the success of a business and so are seeking effective techniques that will allow them to build engagement. Employee engagement has generated a great deal of interest in recent years as a widely used term in organizations and consulting firms (Macey & Schneider, 2008) especially as credible evidence points toward an engagement-profit linkage (Czarnowsky, 2008). Towers Perrin, looking at over 35,000 employees across dozens of companies, showed a positive relationship between employee engagement and sales growth, lower cost of goods sold, customer focus, and reduced turnover.

LITERATURE REVIEW

EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT:

“The extent to which employees commit to something or someone in the organization, and how long they stay as a result of that commitment”. “Engagement is the state in which individuals are emotionally and intellectually committed to the organization as measured by three primary behaviors: Say, Stay and Strive.”

WORKPLACE CULTURE

The workplace culture includes the employee's attitudes, belief systems, value systems, work ethics, behavior that characterize the functioning of a group or organization etc. Workplace culture includes the beliefs, attitudes, practices, norms and customs ('how things are done around here') that characterize a workplace. Workplace culture is also known as organizational or corporate culture. It is defined as a shared belief system of values and processes within an organization. It's been described simply as "the way we do things around here." It is a powerful component to any organization and has both explicit and implicit characteristics.

WORK-LIFE BALANCE POLICIES & PRACTICES

Work-life balance, in its broadest sense, is defined as a satisfactory level of involvement or 'fit' between the multiple roles in a person's life (Hudson, 2005).

There is no one accepted definition of what constitutes a work-life balance practice, the term usually refers to one of the following:

- organizational support for dependent care,
- Flexible work options, and family or personal leave (Estes & Michael, 2005).
- working from home (telework), sharing a full-time job between two employees (job sharing),
- family leave programs (e.g., parental leave, adoption leave, compassionate leave),
- Onsite childcare, and financial and/or informational assistance with childcare and eldercare services.

The policies need to be supported by the workplace culture, which reflects the beliefs, values and norms of the whole of the organisation from the CEO to staff members. Other important factors in the success of work life balance policies include

- Proper communication of commitment to the policies to existing and future employees ,
- Raising awareness of the policies,
- Education of managers about the importance of policies, and
- Training of managers on 'how to' implement these policies.

WORK-LIFE BALANCE DRIVES EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT IN DILIGENCES

Since the last two decades there is a drastic change in the workforce and the needs of employees to effectively manage demanding work schedules and their personal lives. The McCrindle Research study of 3000 Australians shows that work-life balance is the number one factor of job attraction & retention (even above salary). Employers are seeking scarce staff are increasingly touting their commitment to work-life balance in recruitment advertising. But apart from attracting someone into a job, do initiatives to encourage work-life balance also stimulate employee engagement. HR Partner can explore options and create recommendations for making change around programs, such as paid and unpaid time off plans, flexible work arrangements and child and elder care resources.

WORKPLACE CULTURE SETS THE TONE FOR EMPLOYEE INVOLVEMENT

Organizations which create cultures that value balance, and assist employees to achieve life balance will be rewarded with highly engaged employees. By developing more unified and compassionate workplace cultures, organizations will be more attractive to people of all generations. Such studies provide valuable insight and information to HR professionals to assess HR policies and programs for the multigenerational workplace

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the relationship between the work life balance and total employee involvement
- To analyse the present scenario of work life imbalance leads to low employee involvement which influence the productivity and profitability of the any concern.
- To suggest the possible measures of HR policies and programs that will balance the work and life.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The increased demand for work/life balance and the changing relationship between employers and employees are driving the need for HR professionals and their organizations to truly understand that what employees need& want and then determine how to meet those needs while at the same time developing and leveraging workplace talents at all levels

In this study, we have listed some of the needs and wants whichvery essentials to the concerns which will improve the employee involvement.

Scope of Study:

The focus in this study is used to identify the relationship between the work life balance and total employee involvement towards an organisaional activity.

Methodology:

The secondary data was collected from the compilation of IBM, one of Australia’s largest IT companies, is one of the country’s most female-friendly workplaces. This date has provided some of the HR policies and programs and its examples which is needed to employee for improvement of work commitment.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The secondary data was collected from the report of IBM and European Diversity Research & Consulting which may be hidden or forgotten bias and it is not for universal truth.

Table: 1

The table shows the relationship between the two dependent variable of work life balance and employee involvement.

Hypothesis:

H0- work life balance does not has any relationship with the employee involvement

H1- Work life balance has relationship with the employee involvement

Observed frequency table

	Balanced work life	Unbalanced work life	Total
High employee	40	40	80
Low employee	35	85	120
Total	75	125	200

Expected frequency table

	Balanced work life	Unbalanced work life	Total
High employee	$75 \cdot 80 / 200 = 30$	50	80
Low employee	45	75	120
Total	75	125	200

O	E	O-E	(O-E)^2	(O-E)^2/E
40	30	-10	100	3.33
40	50	10	100	2.00
35	45	10	100	2.22
85	75	-10	100	1.33
200	200			8.88

Chi-square test $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$ Calculated value=8.88, Degree of freedom = (No. of columns - No. of rows)= (2-1)(2-1)=1 Table value of χ^2 for 5 dft=3.84

CONCLUSION

Since the calculated value of χ^2 is greater than the table value of χ^2 , H_0 is rejected 5% level. So, E- Work life balance has relationship with the employee involvement

Table 2:

According to European Diversity Research & Consulting the most frequently implemented work-life balance programs in Europe are:

S.No	Needs and wants	Total	Yes	No	Percentage
1.	Part-time work	200	195	5	97.5%
2.	Flexible start and	200	190	10	94.8%
3.	Flexible break times	200	186	14	93.0%
4.	Phased out/phased	200	178	22	89%
5.	Health checks	200	164	36	82%
6.	Part-time work	200	163	37	81.5%
7.	Seminars (stress,	200	160	40	80%
8.	Telecommuting	200	154	46	77%

Calculation through the correlations

Correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 levels (2 tailed) According to the table above, the result shown by Pearson Correlation there is no relationship for both elements. It is because the relationship for the dependent variable and independent variable were negative relationship which means that the R value is -.072.

Interference:

The above figure has explained about the various measures to inculcate the personal stress which is the negative impact of unbalanced work and life pressure. It has given Part time work for employees 97.5% and most of them(94.8%) wished flexible start and finish times. 93% of them need flexible break times, Phased out and phased in part time for 89%, health checkups for 82%, Part time work for managers are 81.5%. Some of them (80%) need seminars and 77% of them need telecommuting

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATION

- The case study indicates that work life balance is directly proportional to total employee involvement which plays a vital role in business activities. The business activities may consist of high production, high sales, and huge profit.
- The failure of balancing the professional and personal work will affect the overall business cycle.
- The company needs to identify the problem and In addition, we recommend making ones values explicit and setting concordant personal and professional goals
- We must all find a variety of strategies, both personal and professional, to assist us in negotiating this balancing act.
- First, we can aim to maximize the fit between ourselves and our jobs by looking for employers that offer the flexibility we need. We can also advocate for increased flexibility in our current jobs, understanding that we may or may not be successful.

CONCLUSION

Balancing our work and personal lives is difficult but incredibly important. It is critical to avoid a pattern of delaying what we value most and prioritizing those things that are ultimately of less value to us. Examining and living by our values, while hard, is a vital step to achieving balance and happiness in our lives. In the personal realm, we recommend a variety of techniques, including consciously slowing down and cultivating mindfulness, which can help us become aware of our thoughts and our physical sensations in the moment. This awareness allows us to hold on to what is important and to lower our stress levels. If our values conflict, we need to wrestle with this discrepancy and make hard decisions. Lastly, we need to take care of ourselves physically, emotionally, and spiritually, and learn to ask for and

accept help. We need to identify sources of support, both emotional and practical, in our families, friends, and communities.

Ultimately, as we grow older, we may feel a sense of regret if we have not lived our lives in concert with our values. During goals of care discussions, we work hard to help our patients understand this. We owe ourselves the same respect and care.

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IMPACT OF SALES PROMOTION: INITIATE EARLIER PURCHASE ON CONSUMER TOWARDS FMCG

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Abstract

Sales promotion as a pivotal component of marketing mix has been heavily used as a major incentive tool to pull consumers to stores and increase short-run sales volumes. Since 1980s, researchers have constantly proposed a variety of concepts to illustrate how sales promotion might affect consumer purchase behavior via overcoming "consumer entropy" inviting consumers to engage in transactions heightening the psychological value associated with the transactions or by providing consumers with a script of purchase behaviour. Although sales promotion has become a ubiquitous element of consumer marketing, large portions of ineffective promotional activities indicate a great need of refining and redirecting the focus of the impact sources. Numerous studies have focused on consumer attitudinal and behavioral responses to price promotion and its utilitarian benefits. But this paper had dealt with initiate the earlier purchase behaviour of the consumers due to sales promotion based on PCP and FHBP products.

INTRODUCTION

Sales promotion is an initiative undertaken by organizations to promote and increase sales, usage or trial of a product or services (Aderemi, 2003). Sales promotion refers to the provision of incentives to customers or to the distribution channel to stimulate demand for a product. It is an important component of an organizations overall marketing strategy along with advertising, public relations and personal selling. Sales promotion acts as a competitive weapon by providing an extra incentive for the target audience to purchase or support one brand over the other. It is particularly effective in spurring product trials and unplanned purchases (Aderemi, 2003). Sales promotion is a marketing activity that adds to the basic value proposition behind a product (i.e. getting more for less) for a limited time in order to stimulate consumer purchasing, selling effectiveness or the effort of the sales force. This implies that, sales promotion may be directed either at end consumer or at selling intermediaries such as retailers or sales crews.

Sales Promotion is indeed an essential component of marketing mix. According to McCarthy (1960) and Borden (1964), marketing mix consists of four 'P's namely Product, Price, Place and Promotion. The Promotion itself is conceptualized as promotion mix consisting of elements like Advertisements, Direct Marketing, Publicity or Public Relations, Personal Selling and Sales Promotion (Kotler, 2003).

SALES PROMOTION CAPABILITIES

1. **Invigorate Sales of a Mature Brand:** Sales promotions cannot reverse the sales decline for an undesirable product or brand. However, sales promotions can invigorate sales of a mature product that requires a shot in the arm.
2. **Neutralize Competitive Advertising and Sales Promotions:** Sales promotions can be used to offset competitors' advertising and sales-promotion efforts.
3. **Obtain Trial Purchases from Consumers:** Marketers depend on free sample, coupons, and other sales promotions to encourage trial purchases of new products. Many consumers would never

try new products or previously untried established brands without these promotional inducements.

4. **Hold Current Users by Encouraging Repeat Purchases:** Strategic use of certain forms of sales can encourage repetitive purchasing, helping reduce brand switching by consumers.
5. **Increase Product Usage by Loading Consumers:** Consumers tend to use more of certain products (e.g., snack foods and soft drinks) when they have more of them available in their homes.
6. **Preempt Competition by Loading Consumers:** When consumers are loaded with one company's brand, they are temporarily out of marketplace for competitive brands. Hence, one brand's sales promotion serves to preempt sales of competitive brands.
7. **Reinforce Advertising:** An advertising campaign can be strengthened greatly by a well coordinated sales promotion effort (Shimp, 1997).

INITIATED EARLIER PURCHASE

Purchase acceleration means that a consumer's purchase timing or purchase quantity is influenced by promotion activities. One possible consequence of purchase acceleration is that it shifts purchases forward that would have occurred anyway. Other effects can take place, however. Purchase time and/or quantity acceleration can prevent switching from the manufacturer's brand. Promotions can also lead to "decelerated" purchase timing, because consumers learn in advance or anticipate that a promotion will occur and wait for the event.

The economic theory as developed by Blattberg et al. (1981) provides one explanation for purchase acceleration and for differences between households. The consumer wants to minimize the costs of satisfying his or her household's demand for the product. By buying on deal at a lower price, the consumer can decrease household purchase costs but may incur a cost of carrying more inventory of the product than is needed to satisfy immediate consumption. Some households, perhaps those with minimal storage space, have high holding costs and will not respond to price deals. Other households have relatively low inventory holding costs and will potentially respond to deals.

There is a good deal of empirical support for the purchase acceleration effects of sales promotions. Several researchers (e.g., Wilson et al. 1979, Shoemaker 1979, Grover and Rao 1985, Neslin et al. 1985, Gupta 1988, Schneider and Currim 1991) have provided empirical evidence that promotions are associated with increased purchase quantity and adjusted interpurchase times. Based on research on two product categories (bathroom tissue and instant coffee) Neslin et al. (1985) concluded that increased purchase quantity is more likely to be exhibited than shortened interpurchase times, but the specific effects were found to depend on the type of promotion. Gupta (1988) estimated that 14 percent of the increase in sales due to promotion is accounted for by accelerated purchase timing, and that 2 percent is accounted for by quantity. Chintagunta estimated respectively 15 and 45 percent.

Bucklin et al. (1998) estimated that 20 percent of the increase in sales due to promotion is accounted for by accelerated purchase timing, and that 22 percent is accounted for by quantity. The empirical generalization offered by Bell et al. (1999) shows that purchase acceleration (timing and/or quantity) differs across households and product categories.

SAMPLES

Primary data was collected from a group of 579 respondents from in and around Chidambaram Town, Cuddalore District, Tamilnadu, India. The respondents were selected through the convenience sampling technique, since the procedure is less time consuming and more convenient.

INTERPRETATION

Table:1 Sales Promotional Impact (Earlier Purchase) based on Consumer Decision Making for Food and Health Beverage Products (FHBP)

ANOVA(b)					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	166.578	6	27.763	5.829	.000(a)
Residual	2724.582	572	4.763		
Total	2891.161	578			

a) **Predictors:** (Constant), **Decision Making:** - Rationalization, Vigilance, Defensive Avoidance, Hyper-vigilance, Buck-passing, Procrastination

b) **Dependent Variable:** Initiate Earlier Purchase – Food and Health Beverage Products (FHBP)

The above table summarizes the results of the analysis of variance. Sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean square are displayed for two sources of variations, regression and residual. The above output for regression displays information about the variations accounted for by the model. The output for a total (2891.161) is the sum of information for regression (166.578) and residual (2724.582). A model with the large regression sum of squares in comparison with residual sum of squares indicates that the model accounts for the most of the variation in the dependent variable. F statistics (5.829) are the regression mean square divided residual mean squared. Regression degree of freedom is the numerated degree of freedom and the residual degree of freedom is the denominator degree of freedom for the 'F' statistics. The total number degree of freedom is the number of cases minus 1. If the significance of 'F' statistics is small (0.05), then the independent variable does a good job in explaining the variation in the dependent variable.

According to the aforementioned studies, it can be said that a study of consumers' decision-making styles is very important to consider when attempting to identify and understand the consumers' shopping behavior and motivation, especially in the FMCG market.

Sl. No.	Decision Making Scale Dimensions {Food and Health Beverage Products}	Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	B		
	(Constant)	3.968	.733		5.412	.000
1.	Vigilance	-.037	.035	-.047	-1.044	.297
2.	Hyper-Vigilance	.126	.048	.119	2.635	.009**
3.	Defensive Avoidance	-.004	.051	-.004	-.083	.933
4.	Procrastination	-.066	.057	-.056	-1.170	.243
5.	Buck Passing	.232	.052	.211	4.447	.000**
6.	Rationalization	.025	.056	.021	.449	.654

Source: Computed Primary Data * *Significant at 1 percent level

$$\hat{Y}=3.968+(-0.037)x_1+(0.126)x_2+(-0.004)x_3+(-0.066)x_4+(0.232)x_5+(.025)x_6$$

Where, \hat{y} is the estimated that sales promotional impact such as initiate the earlier purchase due to offer products from FHB category through decision making dimensions.

McDonald (1993) investigated the roles of shopper decision-making styles in predicting consumer catalogue loyalty and Salleh (2000) analyzed consumers' decision-making styles dimensions across different product classes followed by Bakewell and Mitchell (2003) examined the decision-making styles of adult female Generation consumers in the UK. The above previous studies reveals that the decision making style of consumers has play a important role in marketing research.

The above equation shows the impact of sales promotional such as initiate earlier purchase estimated on consumer's decision making dimensions such as Rationalization, Vigilance, Defensive Avoidance, Hyper-vigilance, Buck-passing and Procrastination. The result of the t- test reveals that the

calculated significance of the partial regression co-efficient -0.037 and .232 were valid at 1 percent level. The f test shows that the explained variation was highly significant at 1 percent level. From the above co-efficient table, it has been concluded that the variables of decision making dimensions namely vigilance and buck passing styles of decision making consumers had accepted the earlier purchase activity when the product available with the offer at present as well as in future.

Table: 2 Sales Promotional Impact (Earlier Purchase) based on Consumer Decision Making for Personal Care Products (PCP)

ANOVA(b)

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	280.173	6	46.696	3.382	.003(a)
Residual	7898.707	572	13.809		
Total	8178.881	578			

a) Predictors: (Constant), Decision Making: - Rationalization, Vigilance, Defensive Avoidance, Hyper-vigilance, Buck-passing, Procrastination

b) Dependent Variable: Initiate Earlier Purchase –Personal Care Products

The above table summarizes the results of the analysis of variance. Sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean square are displayed for two sources of variations, regression and residual. The above output for regression displays information about the variations accounted for by the model. The output for a total (8178.881) is the sum of information for regression (280.173) and residual (7898.707). A model with the large regression sum of squares in comparison with residual sum of squares indicates that the model accounts for the most of the variation in the dependent variable. F statistics (3.382) are the regression mean square divided residual mean squared. Regression degree of freedom is the numerated degree of freedom and the residual degree of freedom is the denominator degree of freedom for the 'F' statistics. The total number degree of freedom is the number of cases minus 1. If the significance of 'F' statistics is small (0.05), then the independent variable does a good job in explaining the variation in the dependent variable.

Consumers are frequently faced with judging the quality of various products, when determine what to buy, in what amount. It may, however, be difficult for consumers to assess the importance of various quality-aspects in relation to each other and in relation to requirements rooted in the intended use of the products (SOU, 1994).

Coefficients(a)

Sl. No.	Decision Making Scale Dimensions	Un standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	B		
	(Constant)	3.117	1.248		2.497	.013
1	Vigilance	-.055	.060	-.041	-.907	.365
2	Hyper-Vigilance	.214	.082	.120	2.621	.009**
3	Defensive Avoidance	-.009	.086	-.005	-.104	.917
4	Procrastination	-.097	.096	-.049	-1.007	.314
5	Buck passing	.263	.089	.143	2.971	.003**
6	Rationalization	.038	.095	.019	.400	.689

$$\hat{Y}=3.117+(-0.041)x_1+(0.120)x_2+(-0.005)x_3+(-0.049)x_4+(0.143)x_5+(.019)x_6$$

Where, \hat{y} is the estimated that sales promotional impact such as initiate the earlier purchase due to offer products from PCP category through decision making dimensions.

Under the influences of different environmental characteristics, consumers' individual characteristics would vary and their perceptions of value and the significance of different product attributes may also be dissimilar. In the extant consumer decision-making literature, most researchers have suggested that several internal and external variables interact to affect consumers' purchase decisions. Product characteristics used by consumers in comparing merchandise are one of the influencing factors affecting consumer decision-making. Consumers' buying decisions are often affected by their perceptions of product attributes in terms of relative importance.

The above equation shows the impact of estimated that sales promotional impact such as initiate the earlier purchase due to offer products from FHB category through decision making dimensions such as Rationalization, Vigilance, Defensive Avoidance, Hyper-vigilance, Buck-passing and Procrastination. The result of the t- test reveals that the calculated significance of the partial regression co-efficient 0.214 and 0.263 were valid at 1 percent level. The f test shows that the explained variation was highly significant at 1 percent level. From the above co-efficient table, it has been concluded that hyper vigilance and buck passing styles of decision making consumers had ready to initiate the earlier purchase due to offer products from PCP category.

SUGGESTIONS

Initiate earlier purchase means one possible consequence of purchase acceleration is that it shifts purchases forward that would have occurred anyway. Other effects can take place, however. Purchase time and/or quantity acceleration can prevent switching from the manufacturer's brand. Promotions can also lead to "decelerated" purchase timing, because consumers learn in advance or anticipate that a promotion will occur and wait for the event. From this study the researcher had found that the variables of decision making dimensions namely vigilance and buck passing styles of decision making consumers had accepted the earlier purchase activity for food and health beverage products when the product available with the offer at present as well as in future but incase of personal care products hyper vigilance and same buck passing style of decision making consumers were accepted the initial purchase activities whether the offers may available on that products. Cost worth products or low cost products have made an involvement in initiate purchase whether it may available in offers.

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FACTORS AFFECTING THE BRAND LOYALTY OF BATH SOAPS: THE CONTEMPORARY OVERVIEW

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ABSTRACT

When consumers become committed to a particular brand and make repeat purchases over time. Brand loyalty is a result of consumer behavior and is affected by a person's preferences. Loyal customers will consistently purchase products from their preferred brands, regardless of convenience or price. Companies will often use different marketing strategies to cultivate loyal customers, be it is through loyalty programs (i. e. rewards programs) or trials and incentives (i.e. samples and free gifts). The extent of the faithfulness of consumers to a particular brand, expressed through their repeat purchases, irrespective of the marketing pressure generated by the competing brands. This paper has analysis of the factors which affecting the brand loyalty of bath soap in various aspects.

DEFINITION OF BRAND LOYALTY

Brand loyalty, in marketing, consists of a consumer's commitment to repurchase or otherwise continue using the brand and can be demonstrated by repeated buying of a product or service or other positive behaviours such as word of mouth advocacy (Dick and Kunal, 1994). Brand loyalty is more than simple repurchasing, however. Customers may repurchase a brand due to situational constraints (such as vendor lock-in), a lack of viable alternatives, or out of convenience (Jones et al., 2002). Such loyalty is referred to as "spurious loyalty". True brand loyalty exists when customers have a high relative attitude toward the brand which is then exhibited through repurchase behaviour (Reichheld and Earl, 1990), (Reichheld, 1993).

INTRODUCTION

There are many operational definitions of brand loyalty. In general, brand loyalty can be defined as the strength of preference for a brand compared to other similar available options. This is often measured in terms of repeat purchase behaviour or price sensitivity (Brandchannel.com, 2006).

Brand loyal consumers are less price-sensitive. A strong consumer franchise gives manufacturers leverage with retailers. And, loyalty reduces the sensitivity of consumers to marketplace offerings, which gives the firm time to respond to competitive moves. In general, brand loyalty is a reflection of brand equity, which for many businesses is the largest single asset. Brand equity reflects the value added to a product that results from brand knowledge. A loyal customer franchise is the most important source of competitive advantage.

Brand Loyalty is the consumer's conscious or unconscious decision, expressed through intention or behaviour, to repurchase a brand continually. It occurs because the consumer perceives that the brand offers the right product features, image, or level of quality at the right price. Consumer behaviour is habitual because habits are safe and familiar. In order to create brand loyalty, advertisers must break consumer habits, help them acquire new habits, and reinforce those habits by reminding consumers of the value of their purchase and encourage them to continue purchasing those products in the future.

PATTERNS OF BRAND LOYALTY BEHAVIOUR

1. Hardcore Loyal - who buy the brand all the time.
2. Soft-core Loyal - loyal to two or three brands.
3. Shifting Loyalty - moving from one brand to another
4. Switchers -with no loyalty (possibly 'deal-prone', constantly looking for bargains or 'vanity prone', looking for something different).

Loyalty includes some degree of pre-dispositional commitment toward a brand. Brand loyalty is viewed as multidimensional construct. It is determined by several distinct psychological processes and it entails multivariate measurements. **Customers' Perceived value, Brand trust, Customers' satisfaction, Repeat purchase behaviour and Commitment are found to be the key influencing factors of brand loyalty.** Commitment and Repeated purchase behaviour are considered as necessary conditions for brand loyalty followed by Perceived value, satisfaction and brand trust (Punniyamoorthy and Prasanna, 2007). The most elaborate conceptual definition of brand loyalty was presented by Jacoby and Chestnut (1978). However, Bloemer and Kasper (1995) defined true brand loyalty as having six necessary conditions which are:

- ✓ the biased (i.e. non-random);
- ✓ behavioural response (i.e. purchase);
- ✓ expressed over time;
- ✓ by some decision-making unit;
- ✓ with respect to one or more alternative brands out of a set of such brands; and
- ✓ a function of psychological processes.

True brand loyalty exists when customers have a high relative attitude toward the brand exhibited through repurchase behaviour. This type of loyalty can be a great asset to the firm: customers are willing to pay higher prices, may cost less to serve and can bring in new customers to the firm (Reichheld and Sasser, 1990). The brand loyal consumer does not attempt any kind of attribute evaluation but simply chooses the familiar brand on the basis of some overall positive feelings towards it. This overall positive evaluation stems from past experience with the particular brand under consideration.

FACTORS AFFECTING BRAND LOYALTY

- Product features,
- Sales Promotion,
- Advertisements,
- Availability,
- Brand image,
- Price, and
- Family influence

NEED OF BRAND LOYALTY

Consumer preference is an important factor of marketing management. Unless a marketing manager has the knowledge of the factors that affect consumer's purchasing patterns, consumers purchasing patterns are likely to be influenced by demographic, economic, psychological and sociological factors. They must find out how consumers translate their desires in to meaningful technical language. Consumers describe what they want, in terms of product benefits such as Functions, characteristics, performance criteria and even manufacturing procedures. A marketing manager must be aware of the reason, why people buy a Soap Since consumers differ in their present and future buying requirement, hence the knowledge of buying of different product helps marketers an identify groups, which represents the greatest sales potentials. Marketing management must know, buyers are really seeking their goods and services. Since the ultimate motive of all the marketing activities is based on consumer satisfaction.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Various authors and researchers continuously emphasize on brands are evaluated on the basis whether they have the strong personality that may or may not match the personality of the consumer. Therefore consumers have strong preference for the product that possesses personality dimensions they look for in a product. So, greater the congruency of personality traits that describe an individual's self-image, stronger and greater the loyalty and preferences towards the brand (Iversen, 2003). At the individual level, brand loyalty is regarded as a consequence of the brand knowledge a consumer has stored in long-term memory (Roehm, 2002). It had been proved that positive reciprocal effects occur only when an average-quality parent brand introduces a successful extension that is similar to the parent brand. One major risk with brand extensions is the possibility of diluting the core brand's equity by creating negative brand associations (Chen & Liu, 2004).

Lau et al. (2006) in his article mentioned that there were seven factors that influenced consumers' brand loyalty towards certain sportswear brands. The factors were: brand name, product quality, price, style, store environment, promotion and service quality.

Famous brand names can disseminate product benefits and lead to higher recall of advertised benefits than non-famous brand names (Keller, 2003). Product Quality encompasses the features and characteristics of a product or service that bears on its ability to satisfy stated or implied needs. In other words, product quality is defined as "fitness for use" or 'conformance to requirement" (Russell and Taylor, 2006).

Though Krishnamurthi and Raj (1991) has showed brand loyal consumers are less price sensitive, we have included price in the factors, because Lau et al. (2006) has taken price as a factor. It might also be found that in the case of brand loyalty of toilet soap users that they are not price sensitive. But, we want to test it in the context of Dhaka City.

Source: Adapted from Dick and Basu (1994); Sheth *et al.* (1999)

TOILET SOAP INDUSTRY IN INDIA

Toilet soap is an important day to day basic requirement of any consumer. It is considered as cleansing and beautifying products which is usually used for cleansing one's body. The toilet soaps market is dominated by several, leading national and global brands and a large number of small brands.. The accepted and quality brands are Hamam, Lux, Power, Dove, . Rexona, Medimix, Cinthol, Pears, Mysore sandal, and Lifebouy. The existence of different brands made the consumers difficult to differentiate each brand from other. It is, therefore, very important to find out the impact of brand loyalty and advertisement lure the consumers. The toilet soap market is fragmented and highly competitive in nature.

In India, Toilet soaps became a lifestyle product in urban homes from the 1960s. Despite steady growth, the market penetration of Toilet soaps remained very badly low. Factors such as misconceptions

among India's that Toilet soaps have harsh chemicals which damage skin in the long run, and high excise duty in the earlier years, contributed to this. Aggressive marketing and decrease in excise duty (from 120 percent in 1993 to 16 percent in 2002) contributed to the rapid growth of the market. Between 1994 and 1998, the Toilet soaps market expanded by two- and-a half time. As of January 2001, the Toilet soaps market in India was worth Rs 85 million according to ORG MARG, market penetration in urban and rural areas was just 36 percent and 12 percent respectively. HLL with value share of 68 percent dominated the market. It was followed by P&G and Cavin Care Ltd.

Irrespective of income level and status people use toilet soap. The frequency of toilet soap might vary due to the individual hygiene practice. Many brands of toilet soaps are available in the market of many different prices. People buy toilet soap according to their own capabilities. In the same price range there are also many brands. So, all the time people have to make purchase decision among many brands. At the time of making purchasing decision, people might consider various factors. People might buy same brand repeatedly. They can switch among few brands or they can switch in lots of brands.

CONCLUSION

The success of a firm depends largely on its capability to attract consumers towards its brands. In particular, it is critical for the survival of a company to retain its current customers, and to make them loyal to the brand. To a large extent, the success of most businesses depends on their ability to create and maintain customer loyalty. In the first place, selling to brand loyal customers is far less costly than converting new customers. In addition, brand loyalty provides firms with tremendous competitive weapons.

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MOBILE BANKING SERVICES – AN OVERVIEW OF CUSTOMER ADOPTION

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ABSTRACT

Mobile banking is an emerging application of mobile commerce that could become an additional revenue source to both banks and telecom service providers. It is a form of service convergence enabled by innovative technologies. Despite the alleged benefits of mobile banking, its acceptance has been short of industry expectations. Advances in telecommunication technologies have enabled organizations such as banks and other financial institutions to offer more online services to their customers. Internet banking is one of such services that many banks have been venturing into with large investment. However, studies show that the adoption and usage by customers in some countries are very low. This paper aims to explain the adoption of mobile banking services.

INTRODUCTION

India is considered a young country in the field of mobile banking and need to grow and promote in this section. Although mobile banking services are offered in most public and private banks, but still many customers have not welcomed to these services because they are not familiar with the way using these services and most important is the lack of confidence to electronic systems(Pedersen, 2005). Mobile phone banking is considered by financial services to be one of the most value-adding and important mobile services available to consumers (Lee et al., 2003). Although large investments have been made in the development of mobile phone banking systems, reports on mobile phone banking utilization show that potential users are not adopting the electronic service at the expected rate (Luarn and Lin, 2005). According to the Gartner Hype cycle for consumer mobile applications (Gartner, 2007) report, the penetration rate of mobile phone banking is only about 1 to 5% of the target audience. From the perspective of banks that developed the mobile banking systems, a vastly improved number of customers must use mobile phone banking in order to justify their investments and operational expenditure.

In the 1990s, the banking sector in India saw greater emphasis being placed on technology and innovation. Banks began to use technology to provide better quality services to their customers and at greater speed. Technological advancement allowed them to offer services like Internet banking and mobile banking, making it convenient for customers to interface with their banks from geographically diverse places. M-commerce is mainly divided into entertainment value-added services, information value-added services and mobile commerce. Mobile commerce comprises mobile banking, mobile payment and mobile purchases. Mobile commerce refers to the emerging arena within which commercial transactions are made possible using handheld mobile devices that are connected through wireless networks. Mobile banking is a part of m-commerce, which is defined as the evolution of the e-commerce paradigm from fixed line networks to wireless. With rapid advance of Internet technologies and diffusion of mobile phones, mobile banking (hereafter m-banking) has gained attention as a viable option in delivering financial services.

ADVANTAGES OF M-BANKING

M-banking provides financial transactions services such as *balance check, fund transfer, and bill payment* via a mobile device such as cell phone, PDA, and smart phone (Sripalawat, Thongmak and Ngarmyarn, 2011). In seeking improvements in customer experience, banking institutions have begun offering various m-banking services. According to the TNS mobile life survey, new m-banking users in countries like China, Brazil, and Kenya has increased dramatically. For instance, percentage of Chinese consumers using m-banking increased from 10% in 2010 to 25% in 2011, and increased from 6% to 18% in Kenya. This growth, however, is not limited to those developing nations. Countries such as UK, USA, and Sweden also have experienced a reasonable growth (Cellular-News, 2011).

From a managerial point of view, m-banking provides new cost-saving opportunities for banks. Benefits include reducing operation costs, minimizing transaction errors and potential for fraud, generating additional revenue through commissions and service fees, and improving customer retention and brand loyalty (Luo, Li, Zhang and Shim, 2010). While m-banking grows in popularity, mobile transactions have not been used as much as expected (Kleijnen, Wetzels and Ruyter, 2004; Suoranta and Mattila, 2004). There are only 200 million m-banking users out of 5 billion mobile users around the world. Even within developed countries where mobile devices have become almost ubiquitous, m-banking adoption rate is still low (Cellular-News, 2011). Consumer skepticism about m-banking is mainly driven by security concerns, financial burdens, and poor accessibility due to handsets and/or wireless network (Kim, Shin and Lee, 2009; Laforet and Li, 2005). Five factors, based on extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), were considered to examine consumers' behavioral intention to adopt mobile banking: perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived credibility, perceived self-efficacy, and perceived financial cost.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mobile Commerce (m-commerce) is defined as a business transaction conducted through mobile communication networks or the Internet (Siau and Shen, 2003). M-banking can offer value to consumers through convenience and flexibility by enabling time and place independence (Kim et al, 2009; Venkatesh et al, 2003). Mobile banking is an application of m-commerce which enables customers to access bank accounts through mobile devices to conduct and complete bank-related transactions such as balancing cheques, checking account statuses, transferring money and selling stocks (Kim et al, 2009; Tiwari and Buse, 2007). Luo et al (2010), defined mobile banking as an innovative method for accessing banking services via a channel whereby the customer interacts with a bank using a mobile device (e.g. mobile phone or personal digital assistant (PDA)).

Obviously, if customers not welcome mobile banking systems, providing these services will fail. Today, despite the late acceptance of mobile banking in India, the banks seem to be aware of opportunities that the technology is provided for them. In fact, they are moving very fast towards a modern mobile banking and providing services to customers in higher levels (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). On the other hand, despite the great investments made in the field of mobile banking, reports indicate that some users not use this technology, though they have access to it So, studying behavioral factors influencing customer adoption of mobile banking will make the banking system to identify factors related to adoption of the technology and to strengthen relevant factors in order to encourage customers to use this service and thus develop the electronic banking. This reveals the need to perform investigations to identify factors determining adoption of the mobile banking system and customers attitude toward it (Laukkanan, 2007). Several theories are offered in order to identify factors that cause people accept new technologies and information systems and use them (Rao and Troshani, 2007), such as Theory of Reasoned Action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), and Decomposed theory of Planned Behavior (Taylor and Todd, 1995).

DEVELOPMENT OF MOBILE BANKING

M-banking can offer unique values to consumers. It enables time and place independence and has effort-saving qualities (Lee & Benbasat, 2003; Mallat et al., 2004). It can also make people work better and increase their control over their affairs. Convenience, ubiquity, flexibility and contextuality are other distinctive elements of m-commerce (Lee & Benbasat, 2003; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Looney et al., 2004). Anckar & D’Incau (2002) classified the benefits of m-commerce in terms of wireless values and mobile values. Wireless values such as cost savings, convenience and efficiency are benefits that mobile devices deliver better than stationary devices do. In addition, mobile values such as contextuality and ubiquity represent advantages unique to mobile commerce. Many studies emphasize the potential value of context-driven m-commerce. Anckar & D’Incau (2002) suggest that m-commerce delivers special customer value when available services are grounded on five value contexts: time-sensitivity (e.g. urgency), spontaneity (as opposed to pre-planned), entertainment needs (e.g. time-filler), efficiency needs (e.g. productivity) and mobility related (e.g. location-based services). Among them, much emphasis has been placed on location-specific or localization services (Barnes, 2003; Looney et al., 2004). Technologies including cellular network and satellite-based positioning enable tracking and monitoring, content provision, controlling and a host of other services with unprecedented levels of customization (Barnes, 2003).

There are, however, challenges associated with m-banking. Above all is the customer’s experience of the user interface in terms of content design and functional ability (Venkatesh et al., 2003). M-banking devices that rely on a small screen, offering limited screen resolution and an uncooperative keypad, may be too difficult for customers to use. M-banking is also vulnerable to information and transaction eavesdropping, and is limited in bandwidth and processing power, connection stability, and functional predictability (Jarvenpaa et al., 2003; Lee & Benbasat, 2003; Siau & Shen, 2003). Lee et al. (2003) also summarized the social and psychological risks of mobile banking: risks of exclusion, seclusion and intrusion. Recognizing the challenges, Lee & Benbasat (2003) proposed design guidelines to offset the weaknesses of mobile devices and improve m-commerce experience.

Fig 1. Process of Mobile Banking Services

FUNCTIONS OF MOBILE BANKING SERVICES

The following functionalities are available:

a. Mobile Banking Service over Application

- Funds transfer (within and outside the bank)
- Immediate Payment Services (IMPS): [Click here for details.](#)
- Enquiry services (Balance enquiry/ Mini statement)
- Cheque book request
- Demat Enquiry Service
- Bill Payment (Utility bills, credit cards, Insurance premium), Donations, Subscriptions
- Mobile /DTH Top up
- M Commerce (Merchant payments, SBI life insurance premium)

b. Mobile Banking Service over SMS:

- Enquiry Services (Balance Enquiry/Mini Statement)
- Mobile Top up
- DTH Top up/ recharge
- IMPS- Mobile to Mobile Transfer
- Change MPIN

c. Mobile Banking Service over USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data)

- Enquiry Services (Balance Enquiry/Mini Statement)
- Mobile Top up
- Funds Transfer (within Bank)

CONCLUSION

Mobile banking is indeed a very powerful tool to deliver the much needed financial services of using technological advancement in the current situation. As service providers can leverage on the high mobile penetration in the banking services for rapid financial inclusion of the heavy banking transactions.

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WTO AND DOMESTIC SUBSIDIES IN INDIAN AGRICULTURE

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ABSTRACT

Domestic support in developed countries led to low international commodity prices which have forced many developing countries are low cost producers of agricultural goods they have not able to complete artificially cheap exports from developed countries

INTRODUCTION

India in its proposal to WTO has categorically pointed out that all Blue and Green Box subsidies are not as minimally trade distorting as it made out an account of the following reasons:

- The ability of farmers to take risk as well as to make farm investments substantially increase provided support in the form of assured payments including de-coupled income support is provided, since payments entail insurance and wealth effects.
- These direct payments encourage greater use of farm inputs and enhance access to technology leading to over - production, which in turn distorts agricultural markets.
- De-coupled or direct payments can be a powerful incentive to maintain or increase current production in the expectation of receiving higher levels of future support.
- De-coupled or direct payments have been found to increase land in farming rather than putting it to some other economically better use.
- De-coupled or direct payments heavily subsidize the cost of production, which enables the receivers of such support to capture a substantial share in the export markets at the cost of more efficient producers.

Table 1 also shows that the 2 percent gain in market share experienced by developing countries happened mostly because of good export performance of countries from Latin America and the Caribbean

(Mainly due to good export performance of Brazil, Argentina and Mexico).

Table 1. Share of Developing Countries in World Agricultural Exports by Region, 1990-2003(Percentage)

	1990	1995	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	2003
All Developing Countries	39	39 1/2	39 1/2	40	41 1/2	42	40	40	41	41 1/2
Of Which:										
Africa	6	5 1/2	5 1/2	5	5 1/2	5 1/2	4 1/2	4 1/2	5	5
Developing Asia	15	16 1/2	16	15 1/2	16	16 1/2	16	15 1/2	16 1/2	16 1/2
Latin America and Caribbean	16	15 1/2	16	17 1/2	18	17 1/2	17	17 1/2	17 1/2	17 1/2
Middle East	2	2	2	2	2	2 1/2	2 1/2	2 1/2	2 1/2	2 1/2

Calculations based on the data provided in the WTO document (TN/AG/S/19) shows that India's share in world agricultural exports over the period 1995 to 2001. India's farm exports have marginally from 1.77 percent in 1995 to 1.87 percent in 2003.

Table-2 also shows that even in nominal terms (current US Dollars), India registered a decline in agricultural exports over the period 1995 to 2001. India's farm exports have marginally recovered in the last two years reported in the WTO study.

Table 2. Agricultural Export of Twelve Developing Asian Countries 1990-2003.

	Value OF Agricultural Exports					Share in Total Agricultural Exports		
	1995	2000	2001	2002	2003	1995	2000	2003
	Million USD (Values in current US dollars)					Percentage		
China	11,483	11,951	11,950	13,514	15,974	3.81	4.11	4.52
Malaysia	6,907	5,461	5,319	7,211	8,995	2.29	1.88	2.54
Thailand	6,864	6,094	6,487	6,751	8,043	2.27	2.10	2.28
India	5,345	5,072	5,089	5,612	6,616	1.77	1.75	1.87
Indonesia	3,700	4,239	3,761	5,347	5,667	1.23	1.46	1.60
Singapore	4,371	2,849	2,597	2,740	2,608	1.45	0.98	0.74
Republic of Korea	1,669	1,596	1,673	1,706	1,935	0.55	0.55	0.55
Philippines	1,875	1,529	1,531	1,510	1,867	0.62	0.53	0.53
Pakistan	1,122	1,088	1,040	1,083	1,217	0.37	0.37	0.34
Chinese Taipei	2,927	1,019	939	939	976	0.97	0.35	0.28
Hong Kong, China	669	351	323	345	362	0.22	0.12	0.10
Macao, China	78	36	36	49	55	0.03	1001	0.01
Total of Above	47,010	41,285	40,745	46,807	54,315	15.58	14.21	15.37
Total Developing Asia	49,783	46,499	45,985	50,735	58,322	16.5	16	16.5

From time - series data it is notable that between 1995-96 and 2003-04, India's agricultural trade surplus has shown a decline (Table 3). This again highlights the fact that like most other developing countries, the anticipated gains from the AoA have mostly eluded India. The Table also shows that India's agricultural trade virtually stagnated for most part of the part of the WTO period : only to recover marginally in the past two years (Table 3). Continued distortion of the global agricultural trade market is said to be one main reason behind this poor performance of India in the agriculture trade front

Table 3: India's Agricultural trade before and after WTO, Million \$.

YEAR	IMPORT	EXPORT	TRADE SURPLUS
1990-91	672	3352	2680
1991-92	604	3203	2599
1992-93	938	2950	2012
1993-94	742	4013	3271
1994-95	1891	4211	2320
1995-96	1761	6098	4337
1996-97	1863	6806	4943
1997-98	2364	6685	4321
1998-99	3462	6064	2602
1999-2000	3708	5842	2134
2000-01	2646	6273	3627
2001-02	3408	6234	2826
2002-03	3542	7161	3619
2003-04	4765	8029	3264

It is observed that domestic support in developed countries not only insulates the markets of countries and threatens the domestic markets of developing countries also negatively affect market access of developing countries in the third countries in the third country markets by distorting the prices in those markets. Therefore, it is imperative that this round of negotiations try to correct the prevailing problems of global agricultural trade by ensuring more effective reduction of subsidies.

Agricultural policies are disastrous. If those farmers aren't being kept out of export markets by quotas or tariffs, they are being undercut in domestic markets by heavily subsidized produce from the developed world. While some have argued that rich-world subsidies are a net boon to poor countries because they provide cheap food to the masses, in those countries the poorest are often rural farmers, whose lives would be improved by higher prices for their products.

Subsidies in developed countries have affected the trading pattern of a number of Indian agricultural products. The example of rice can be pertinent here. During the early 1990s, India removed restrictions on rice exports. Following the removal of export restrictions, India emerged as a major rice exporting country. However, just after the Asian crisis, international price of rice started declining. Low demand from some big importers of rice from Asia and Latin America was one of the reasons behind this decline. On the supply side, India and China's entry as an exporter in the international rice market and domestic policies undertaken by developed countries increased the supply - demand gap. This decline in international prices of rice was accentuated by heavy subsidization of rice farmers in USA.

It can be argued that in a free trade regime, producers of uncompetitive commodities should shift to the commodities where the country is internationally competitive. Under the current set of circumstances, this basically suggests that farmers of this country should diversify towards the cultivation of cash crops. However, this argument does not take into account the fact that for small and medium farmers of poor developing countries, it is not easy to shift from one crop to another. Low capital, inadequate rural credit which results from increased withdrawal of state and lack of information about the international commodity market conditions make it difficult for the farmers to make this transition. Also it is important to recognize the diversification is crucially dependent, it will be extremely risky for small and medium farmers to diversify into nonfood grain crops.

Opening up of the agriculture sector has also introduced a new element of risk in the system. International commodity prices are highly volatile in nature. A study by Pal (2004)¹ shows that for a large number of commodities, price volatility has actually increased in the post UR period. In a tariff only regime, the instability of international commodity prices is likely to be transmitted directly to the domestic market. High volatility of agricultural commodities alters the risk perception of farmers and introduces a speculative element in agricultural prices. This is likely to have serious implications for farmers in India. In fact, committees looking at the issue of suicide by farmers in Andhra Pradesh have found that the volatility of crop prices has been a major source of income instability and distress for farmers.

Higher returns from some export oriented cash crops like tobacco and sunflower have lured even smaller farms to undertake cash crop cultivation at the expense of traditional crops including food grains. This is risky move because these farmers are now totally dependent upon the revenue from the cash crops are even for their domestic consumption. International prices for cash crops even are volatile and fluctuate widely from year to year. Every losses for farmers. The farmers who do not maintain a cushion of self- produced food grains to support them; such losses can cushion huge food security problems. In southern part of India, there have been numerous cases of farmer suicides because of this reason

To a large extent the decline and volatility of international commodity prices can be attributable to the subsidy regime in developed countries. Findings of the WTO Dispute settlement Board (DSB) on sugar and cotton subsidies, over production of subsidized products and the consequent decline in international commodity prices. This brings the issue of interaction between domestic subsidies and market access into the picture. If rate is unlikely to be required for the protection of any commodity, protection of any commodity, to counter the threat of subsidies and market access into the picture.

protection of any commodity, to counter the threat of subsidies and artificially low international commodity prices it is important to allow for some headroom in the form of difference between bound and applied tariff rates and flexibility in tariff application. Therefore, India should be careful about its market access strategy. In this context, in the current round of negotiation developing countries should link the issue of tariff reduction with the level of subsidization in developed countries.

However it must be mentioned here that in the current round of negotiations, there are indications that a SSSG type instrument will also be made available to developing countries. Moreover, there are talks about providing additional protection to someone agricultural commodities in the form 'Special Products' and 'Sensitive Products'. If these new instruments are made available, then the need for the additional headroom in the application of tariff rates may be less.

CONCLUSION

As far as India is concerned, it appears that the WTO subsidy disciplines introduced are not going to have a constraining impact on the domestic subsidies given to the farm sector in this country. India's farm subsidy levels are well below the 'de minimis' level prescribed by the AoA and it is unlikely that India will be hitting the 'de minimis' level either in the product specific or non product specific subsidies in anytime soon

The Poor performance of India's agricultural trade in the post WTO period can be largely attributed to the distortions of the international agricultural trade market. On one hand, India wants substantial reduction in domestic subsidies in developed countries. On the other hand, it proposes that there should be sufficient flexibility in the rules to allow developing countries pursue support measures towards non-trade concerns like poverty alleviation, rural development, rural employment and diversification of agriculture.

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3. See 'Report of the Commission on Farmers Welfare', Government of Andhra Pradesh, dated April 7th 2005, available at: http://www.macrosan.net/pol/apr05/pol070405Andhra_Pradesh.htm
4. The basic argument is that continued subsidization of agriculture and the dominance of a few developed countries in world agricultural trade have not allowed other countries to join the international farm trade. As a result, the depth of international agriculture trade market has not increased. Therefore; price of agricultural goods remains as volatile as before.
5. For detailed discussion on these see 'Special Products' Options for Negotiating Modalities' by Anwarul Hoda, ICTSD, 2005. Available at <http://www.ictsd.org/dlogue/2005-06-16/Hoda.pdf>.
6. WTO Document number G/AG/NG/W/102, Proposals by India in the areas of: i. Food Security, ii. Market Access, iii. Domestic Support, and iv. Export competition: date 15/01/2001

A MANAGERIAL PERSPECTIVE OF BRAND LOYALTY

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ABSTRACT

Today, the importance of marketing managers knowing how to influence customer loyalty is constantly growing. With competition increasing day after day, customer maintenance and growth has become the first goal of many companies and loyal customers can be considered as a key to success in many service businesses. Brand loyalty is a function of both behaviour and attitudes. It is a consumer's preference to buy a particular brand in a product category. It occurs because consumers perceive that the brand offers the right product features, image, or level of quality at the right price. This perception becomes the foundation for new buying habits. Consumers will initially make a trial product of the brand and when satisfied with the purchase, tend to form habits and continue to purchase the same brand because the product is safe and familiar.

DEFINITION OF 'BRAND LOYALTY'

A brand loyalty as a consumers' decision, expressed through intention or behavior, to repurchase a brand on a regular basis. This kind of decision can be made both on conscious as well as unconscious basis. It occurs because the consumer perceives that the brand offers the right product features, image, or level of quality at the right price. Wilkie (1994) defined brand loyalty as "a favorable attitude toward, and a consistent purchase of, a particular brand". This definition suggests that consumers are loyal when both attitude and behavior are favorable. Jacoby and Chestnut (1978) offered a deeper definition of brand loyalty, stating that brand loyalty is..” biased, behavioral response, expressed over time, by some decision making unit, with respect to one or more brands out of set of such brands, and is a function of psychological processes“.

INTRODUCTION

When consumers become committed to one brand and make repeat purchases over time. Brand loyalty is a result of consumer behavior and is affected by a person's preferences. Loyal customers will consistently purchase products from their preferred brands, regardless of convenience or price. Companies will often use different marketing strategies to cultivate loyal customers, be it is through loyalty programs (i. e. rewards programs) or trials and incentives (i.e. samples and free gifts). The extent of the faithfulness of consumers to a particular brand, expressed through their repeat purchases, irrespective of the marketing pressure generated by the competing brands.

Loyalty matrix

		Predicted loyalty (based on attitudes)		
		Low	Moderate	High
Actual loyalty (based on behaviour)	Low			PROSPECTS
	Moderate	VULNERABLES		
	High			REAL LOYALS

Baldinger and Rubinson (1996) have divided loyal consumers into different groups according to their levels of behavioral and attitudinal loyalty. The key concept of their behavior/attitude matrix is that a brand's loyal substance is not just its behaviorally high loyal customers but also those who show loyalty both in their actions and their attitudes. This framework that is presented in below figure shows, that genuinely loyal consumers, the "real loyal" are loyal both in behaviorally and have strong positive attitudes towards the brand.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Customer loyalty is defined as a customer who repurchases from the same service provider whenever possible, and who continues to recommend or maintains a positive attitude towards the service provider (Bloemer et al., 1999, Gremler and Brown 1999, Shoemaker and Lewis 1999, Kandampully and Suhartanto 2000). Customers may be loyal due to high switching barriers or lack of real alternatives. Customers may also be loyal because they are satisfied and thus want to continue the relationship. History has proven that most barriers to exit are limited with regard to durability; companies tend to consider customer satisfaction the only viable strategy in order to keep existing customers. Several authors have found a positive correlation between customer satisfaction and loyalty (Bearden, Teel et al. 1980; Bolton and Drew 1991; Fornell 1992; Anderson and Sullivan 1993).

Customer loyalty is a buyer's overall attachment or deep commitment to a product, service, brand, or organization (Oliver, 1999). Oliver, (1999) defines loyalty as a deeply held commitment to re-buy product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same brand or same-brand set purchasing. From all previous studies about customer loyalty and the factors that affecting on it such as service quality, switching barriers, and brand image, all researchers gave several definitions of customer loyalty, each definition expect type of product or service, but there are some things are similarity between their definitions as, repeatedly purchase a goods or service over time; and hold favorable attitudes towards a goods or service, or towards the company supplying the goods or service. But the deference between their definitions are the factors that affecting on customer loyalty for example the factors that affecting on loyalty to cars are deferent the factors that affecting on loyalty on mobile phone or any product that consume it daily, monthly or yearly, as mentioned by (Jun and Bin, 2005).

PROCESS OF BRAND LOYALTY

The usual process of brand loyalty generation is that initially, a consumer makes a trial purchase of a specific product from a given brand. If the product meets the customer's expectations and gives satisfaction, the consumer often forms a habit of buying this same product. The consumer is now more willing to buy the product again as well as other products from the same brand, because the brand is now considered safe and it has proven itself to be of sufficient quality. Consumers who are loyal are committed to a brand, willing to pay a higher price for a certain brand over others, and readily recommend the given brand to other people they know (Giddens & Hofmann, 2002). Reichheld and Schefter (2000) explain the generation of brand loyalty in much simpler terms, stating that loyalty is won through delivery of superior customer experience. Kevin Stirtz (2008) suggests six steps in order to create brand-loyal customers.

- ✓ The first step involves asking the customers what they want, in the broadest sense of the question. This includes what they want in general, what they are trying to accomplish, what image they are trying to portray, how they want to be served, and so on.
- ✓ The second step is communicating to your customers what they should expect from the brand. It is of no use to try and please everyone and try to be all things. That kind of strategy usually ends up in too many things half-heartedly and satisfying no one. Instead, companies should figure out their core competencies and focus on them, delivering outstanding products and services in a given area.

- ✓ The third step that Stirtz suggests is to create easy ways for the customers to provide feedback. This step is forgotten by many companies. Companies should be creative in finding ways to get customer feedback, and make sure that the customers know about these ways.
- ✓ The fourth step, which is closely related to the third one, is listening to what your customers say. This includes both utilizing the customer feedback, as suggested in the third step, but also other ways people communicate about the brands, such as the Internet. This process needs to be done on a regular basis.
- ✓ The fifth step is a direct continuation of the fourth one, namely acting on these customer feedback and suggestions.
- ✓ The final step is that of repetition. The whole process needs to be repeated constantly in order to be successful and generate higher levels of loyalty.

TYPES OF BRAND LOYALTY

Building brand loyalty has become a crucial aspect of a business especially these days when the competition in the business world is growing tougher. Remember that the brand loyalists can make or break a brand image by word of mouth promotion. Brand loyalists have that power because a brand survives on the usage of its products or services by the customers. With the development of advanced marketing tools all the brands are competing to reach their target market. Most of them are trying to offer quality product or service at a reasonable rate. So protecting brand switching among customers has become very difficult. Before you know how to build a brand you should have an idea about the 4 types of customers or brand users.

- **Hard Core Brand Loyalists:** These are customers who remain loyal to a single brand.
- **Soft Core Brand Loyalists:** These are customers who remain loyal to 2-3 brands at a time.
- **Shifting Brand Loyalists:** Shifting brand loyalists are those who keep shifting from one brand to another. But they can come back to the brand towards which they were loyal.
- **Switchers:** The switchers always look for new brands. They prefer to experiment with different brands. At times they also switch to new brands because of price change.

EFFECTS OF BRAND LOYALTY

Giddens and Hofmann (2002) mention three important outcomes that are the backbone of the importance of brand loyalty. The first reason pointed out is that companies with high brand loyalty enjoy higher sales volumes. According to Giddens and Hofmann's studies, the average company loses around 13% of their customer base every single year, and that shows just how challenging it can be in the competitive environment of the modern world. To achieve a mere 1% annual growth, the sales need to increase by 14% to both new and existing customers. By reducing customer loss, business growth can be dramatically improved and brand loyalty can be increased. Those two factors lead to more consistent sales of greater volumes, due to the fact that the same brand is purchased repeatedly. The second reason for the importance of brand loyalty mentioned is premium pricing ability. Giddens and Hofmann state that with increased levels of brand loyalty, consumers become less price-sensitive. Overall, they are ready to pay higher amounts for their preferred brand because they sense some special and unique value in that given brands that other brands do not provide. On top of that, brand loyal customers are less prone to chase after discounts. The third and final reason mentioned is related to product search. Those customers loyal to a certain brand are ready to search for that brand and are less sensitive to competitors. This results in lower advertising costs, marketing costs, and distribution costs. Attracting a new customer costs up to four to six times as it does to retain an already existing one.

CONCLUSION

Consumer satisfaction leads to brand loyalty. Satisfaction means a positive evaluation of a product or brand, which shows the consumers that they are capable of making the right decision when choosing from the enormous supply of products. It also shows the consumers that their needs and wants are fulfilled. This is an assumption made very often in marketing theory as well as in

marketing practice. Based on this assumption, every producer of any kind of product (service or goods) should attach utmost importance to creating consumer satisfaction. It is even often supposed that the greater the amount of consumer satisfaction, the greater the degree of brand loyalty and brand loyalty is one of the most important pillars for a firm's continuity (and profits).

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A STUDY ON WORK STRESS OF FEMALE FACULTY MEMBERS IN COLLEGES IN VILLUPURAM DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

Faculty(both government and private colleges)frequently suffer from stress owing among other factors, to the characteristics and physical working conditions typically found in their working place. It is estimated that work stress costs the nations billions of dollars a year in lost outputs, health care expenses and stress related lawsuits (National institute for occupational safety and health-2005).Work stress is a timely and important topic for workers, that is the condition in which some factors or combination of factors interferes with the worker to disrupt her physical, psychological or behavioural effect most affected persons by this problems particularly female who irrespective of the unit(public or private)in which they work frequently suffer from stress. Several studies point out those lecturers, assistant professors, HODs report that they feel stress in their work. Through their dealings with suffering, illness they confront existential issues on a daily basis. They have to cope with stress at work and even in their family lives.

INTRODUCTION

Women in the professoriate are more stressed out than men. That's probably not shocking to female professors (or many of their male colleagues). Academic jobs are oversized and growing larger. The economic realities of academia mean that universities require faculty to teach more courses than ever before, while maintaining active research programs, obtaining significant grants and other sources of funding, and mentoring and advising students. Academic careers pose tripartite demands of research, teaching, and service; at many institutions--perhaps the majority--professors find that campus time is taken up mostly by the latter two, leaving research and writing for evenings and weekends - time that many women need to keep up their homes and raise their families. Regardless of whether they hold a career, women tend to shoulder a greater proportion of domestic work than do men, and they typically balance multiple conflicting roles--professional, mother, house worker, etc. When domestic work is coupled with a busy professional life, the workload can become burdensome, and it increases significantly with each child. Many (especially younger, untenured) women in the academy chronically face a difficult choice: to do the research they must do to keep their jobs and earn tenure or complete essential domestic obligations. Many academic women feel that their career opportunities are limited after having children. Colleagues may assume that they have sold out and are no longer committed to their careers--which may influence tenure, promotion, and other opportunities for advancement (like appointment to chairs, deanships, and high-profile committees). Even women who attempt to circumvent the maternal wall by having children during graduate school often are penalized.

PROBLEMS STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

Within the general area of occupational stress, teaching has been identified as one of the most stressful occupations in many countries. Teaching related stress, commonly termed 'teacher stress' is defined as a teacher's experience of "unpleasant, negative emotions, such as anger, anxiety, tension, frustration, or depression, resulting from some aspect of their work as a teacher. Like other forms of occupational stress, it can have serious implications for the healthy functioning of the individual as well as for the organisation in which the individual serves. At a personal level, teaching related stress can affect a teacher's health, well-being, and performance. From an organisational perspective, it translates to unproductive employee behaviours such as alienation, apathy, and absenteeism. Hence, even after nearly

three decades of research effort, the study of teacher stress, particularly its sources and manifestations, continues to attract widespread interest and attention.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To examine the physiological, psychological and behavioural causes for the stress among respondents.
2. To find out whether socio-economic life is affected due to work stress.
3. To study whether the skills are same for different experienced faculty members.
4. To offer suggestion for reducing stress among the female staff.

HYPOTHESIS:

There is no relationship between workload and stress level.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY/SAMPLING DESIGN:

At present there are all 34 (public and private) colleges in and around villupuram district. A well designed questionnaire has been administered by the researcher himself for the above mentioned colleges. This study involves collection of primary and secondary data. The questionnaire contained three major segments. The first segment consists of general profile. The second segment consists of perception about their work and stress, its impact on family life and its impact on physical, psychological and behavioural impact. The third segment consists of suggestion to reduce and manage stress in personal and organizational view. Random samples of 110 have taken from faculty members of various departments.

TOOLS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Some of the statistical tools used for the analysis of the data were percentage method and chi-square test. For all the percentage method is used to know the percentage proportion of the variables. Chi-square test is used test whether workload and stress. Anova test or F-test is used to test whether mean of two variables skill and experience are significant, does it make any difference.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

“Staff stress is a critical problem for human service professions.(Shinn, Rosario, Morch and Chestnut,1994)teaching is one of the most stressful professions, with a great degree of job stress. Job stress is a psychological syndrome in response to chronic exposure to emotional and interpersonal stressors on the job.(Maslach, schaufeli and leitur 2011).

National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health(NIOSH)estimates that more than 9000 staff members and other teaching professionals are injured or verbally or physically affected on the job everyday, Shirleycayton. Feelings of stress develop from various events, such as work overload, criticism, negligent co-workers, unco-operative peers, lack of support from their head.(Motowidlo, Manning and Packard,1996).

ANALYSIS RESULTS:

Causes of stress:

I.(Physiological, psychological and behavioural)from the listed factors causing stress at work the respondent says less staff causes stress is 14.4% shift working is 12.58%,problem with co workers is 11% majorly as highest to the total percentage.

Other factors also causing stress with lesser difference of the factor causing maximum stress. i.e. lack of facilities and lack of reward, inferior quality instruments, non availability of advanced technology is 25%,lack of cooperation is 9%,improper instruction, time pressure and managing emotions of superiors, management and their family members is around 10%.

EFFECTS OF STRESS:

The effect and symptoms of stress will be realized more when the respondent is depressed it is 69%,sleeping disorder is 65%,digestive system disorder is 26.36%,increase in blood pressure is 21.81% and anxiety is 24.54% are the major effects

Effect of socio-economic(family)life due to work stress 64% of the total respondent says that work stress have impact on family life due to shift basis, full time ,spend less time with family members, working even on government holidays, travelling long distance, no time to look after the children's and elders at home etc.

OVERALL STRESS EFFECT:

On the whole the survey reveals that maximum effect of stress is on the psychological aspect is 65%,physiological is the next about 22.72% and lastly behavioural aspect is 13%.So from this survey it understood that the effect of stress is maximum on psychology(Mental state).Rather than physical.

SKILL IS SAME FOR DIFFERENT EXPERIENCED STAFF

Skills / Exp.yrs	High efficiency	Good	Better	Poor	Total
<1	1	4	0	0	5
Above 1-3	10	34	15	0	59
Above 3-5	1	29	6	0	36
More 5	2	8	0	0	10
Total	14	75	21	0	110

*Use coding method subtracting 20 for the given data

Correction factor =(Total)²/Total no. of rows and column

=(-210)²/16=2756.25

Degree of freedom=(No. of columns-1)=3 Degree of freedom=(No. of rows-1)=3

Residual or error sum of square=Total sum of squares-(sum of squares between columns + sum of squares between rows)=409.23

ANOVA TABLE

	Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F
Between columns	809.25	3	MSC=269.75	MSC/MSE=5.93
Between rows	469.25	3	MSR=156.41	MSR/MSE=3.43
Residual or Error	409.25	9	MSE=45.47	
Total sum of squares	1687.75	15		

The table value of F for(3,9)at 5%level of significance is 3.86,the calculated values of F for skills is 5.93 greater than the table value, hence there is significant difference between skills. The table value of F for (3,9)at 5% level of significance is 3.86,the calculated values of F for experience is 3.43 less than the table value, Hence experience does not make significant difference. Because there are human capacity, knowledge, standard(Expectation to perform),environment, motivation, interpersonal skills, educational level and etc., which determines skills level of an individual.

Hypothesis: There is no relationship between work load and stress

Factors	Yes	No	Total
Work load	57	53	110
Stress	81	29	110
Total	138	82	220

Null Hypothesis (Ho):There is no significant relationship between workload and stress.

Alternate Hypothesis(H1):There is significant relationship between work load and stress

O	E	(O-E)*2	(O-E)*2/E
81	69	144	2.086957
57	69	144	2.086957
29	41	144	3.512195
53	41	144	3.512195
			11.1983

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum(O-E)^2}{E} = 11.1983$$

Degree of Freedom $= (r-1)(c-1) = (2-1)(2-1) = 1$, 5% level of significant at 1 degree of freedom $= 3.841$, the calculated value of χ^2 is greater than the table value. Hence Null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. Therefore there is a relationship between workload and stress.

FINDINGS

a) The survey of female faculty regarding their work stress reveals that less staff, shift work, lack of co-operation, lack of facilities, amenities, lack of advanced technology are the major (psychological, physiological and behavioral) causes of stress.

b) More stress brings out the depression, sleeping disorder, digestive system disorder, anger, and blood pressure, anxiety as a major and maximum effect.

c) Socio-economic life is affected in great extent. More stress effect is only on the psychological state of respondent.

d) There is a relationship between the work load and stress.

SUGESSTIONS

Sl.No	Organization measure to reduce stress at work	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Awards for efficient service	50	45.45
2	Salary hike & other rewards	39	35.45
3	Proper supply of aids and amenities	48	43.63
4	Appointing more staffs	69	62.72
5	Providing quarters, schools etc.	78	70.90
6	Work pressure for providing better results	50	45

In order to give happy family and stress free life for female staff working in colleges ,the management and government should provide quarters for stay near colleges to avoid travelling long distance, schools for children in the nearby premises so that faculty can look after their children, colleges providing facilities exclusively for staff gives a sense of belongingness.

To reduce the stress due to workand work load, the administration have a procedure for purchasing instruments for every departments, necessary documents have been maintained and handed over to the staff in charge of the concern department for which the purchase is made, fill up the vacancy position by appointing right number of staff, encourage by giving awards for efficient service, faculty should working with service mind.

In order to render efficient service and to have stress free mind in general, the faculty should identify the source that cause stress in the domestic life and remove it if possible or control the situation or take it in positive sense. It is suggested to faculty, it’s always better to keep elders, children’s to take care of family in their absence, making interactions with family members and friends, sharing the moments of happiness and sorrows, make time for vacations, plan and prioritize the work and doing it at the right time, having good sleep for 6 to 8 hours, practicing relaxation methods like deep breathing, meditation, yoga, exercise and having a balanced diet and setting realistic goals in order to avoid stress in domestic life.

CONCLUSION

Health is just free from the disease to realize one’s potential. This stress which is unavoidable has become an inherent part of life. The study was made on women staffs who are paid by the government, where to work with all their effort, will have much stress, the study was also made on the fresh staff also. This study reveals that women staff has come to this profession in order to provide service to the needy one and felt this as a respectable blessed profession prominently. Sometimes go dissatisfied as they have limited co-operation, decision making on their own, short of staff to cover etc., and many other reasons on the management part to provide as well family obligations and support from their side. This stressful state is responsible by both the staff members and administration, so the management have to take measures suggested to provide stress free environment also individual has to take effort to free themselves by balancing the work life, changing perception of stress, doing work with service mind, building good relationship with their colleague, work with smiling face and has to practice relaxation methods etc.,

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AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF AGRICULTURAL LABOUR IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

In today's world the agricultural sector employs half of the world's labour force with an estimated 1.3 billion workers active in agricultural production worldwide. The majority of agricultural workers are found in developing countries. A great majority are small scale farmers. They have been more often victims rather than beneficiaries of the green revolution, the technological development and the globalization trends which characterized the 20th century.

Agriculture is one of the three most hazardous sectors of activity, both in industrialized and developing countries. According to estimates from the International Labour Office (ILO), some 170,000 agricultural workers are killed each year. This means that workers in agriculture run at least twice the risk of dying on the job as compared with workers in other sectors. Agricultural mortality rates have remained consistently high in the last decade as compared with other sectors, where fatal accident rates have decreased. Millions of agricultural workers are seriously injured in workplace accidents with agricultural machinery or poisoned by pesticides and other agrochemicals. Furthermore, due to the widespread under-reporting of deaths, injuries and occupational diseases in agriculture, the real picture of the occupational health and safety of farm workers is likely to be worse than what official statistics indicate.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural Labour

Unlike industrial labour, agricultural labour is difficult to define. The reason is that unless capitalism develops fully in agriculture, a separate class of workers depending wholly on wages does not come up. According to the National Commission on Labour "an agricultural labourer is one who is basically unskilled and unorganised and has little for its livelihood, other than personal labour." Thus, persons whose main source of income is wage, employment fall in this category. Mishra and Puri have stated that "All those persons who derive a major part of their income as payment for work performed on the farms of others can be designated as agricultural workers. For a major part of the year they should work on the land of the others on wages."

One of the most distinguishing features of the rural economy of India has been the growth in the number of agricultural workers, cultivators and agricultural labourers engaged in crop production. The phenomena of underemployment, under-development and surplus population are simultaneously manifested in the daily lives and living of the agricultural labourers. They usually get low wages, conditions of work put an excessive burden on them, and the employment which they get is extremely irregular. Agricultural workers constitute the most neglected class in Indian rural structure. Their income is low and employment irregular. Since, they possess no skill or training, they have no alternative employment opportunities either. Socially, a large number of agricultural workers belong to scheduled castes and scheduled tribes. Therefore, they are a suppressed class. They are not organised and they cannot fight for their rights. Because of all these reasons their economic lot has failed to improve even after four decades of planning.

In most countries only some categories of agricultural workers are covered by national legislation, employment injury benefits or insurance schemes. A large number of agricultural workers are thus deprived of any form of social protection. When national regulations exist, they are often

sporadically applied. Effective enforcement is poor due to insufficient labour inspection, lack of understanding and training on hazards and their prevention of both of employers and workers and low levels of organization among agricultural workers.

CLASSIFICATION OF AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS:

Agricultural labourers can be divided into four categories -

1. Landless Labourers, who are attached to the land lords;
2. Landless labourers, who are personally independent, but who work exclusively for others;
3. Petty farmers with tiny bits of land who devote most of their time working for others and
4. Farmers who have economic holdings but who have one or more of their sons and dependants working for other prosperous farmers.

The first group of labourers have been more or less in the position of serfs or slaves, they are also known as bonded labourers.

Agricultural labourers can also be divided in the following manner :

1. Landless agricultural labourers
2. Very small cultivators whose main source of earnings due to their small and sub-marginal holdings is wage employment. Landless labourers in turn can be classified into two broad categories :
 1. Permanent Labourers attached to cultivating households. **March- 2007**
 2. Casual Labourers. The second group can again be divided into three subgroups :
 - (i) Cultivators
 - (ii) Share croppers
 - (iii) Lease holders.

CHARACTERISTICS OF AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS

1. AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS ARE SCATTERED

Agricultural labour in India is being widely scattered over 5.6 lakh villages, of which half have population of less than 500 each. And therefore, any question of building an effective organization, like that of industrial workers, poses insurmountable difficulties. Thus as the vast number of agricultural labour lies scattered all over India, there has been no successful attempt for long, to build their effective organization even at the state level not to speak of the national level.

2. AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS ARE UNSKILLED AND LACK TRAINING

Agricultural labourers, especially in smaller villages away from towns and cities, are generally unskilled workers carrying on agricultural operation in the centuries old traditional wages. Most of them, especially those in small isolated villages with around 500 populations, may not have even heard of modernization of agriculture. Majority of them are generally conservative, tradition bound, totalistic and resigned to the insufferable lot to which according to them fate has condemned them. There is hardly any motivation for change or improvement. Since, there is direct supervision by the landlord, there is hardly any escape form hard work and since there is no alternative employment. The agricultural labourer has to do all types of work-farm and domestic at the bidding of the landlord.

3. UNORGANISED SECTOR

Agricultural labourers are not organized like industrial labourers. They are illiterate and ignorant. They live in scattered villages. Hence they could not organize in unions. In urban areas workers could generally organize themselves in unions and it is convenient for political parties to take interest in trade union activities. This is almost difficult in case of farm labour. Accordingly, it is difficult for them to bargain with the land owners secure good wages.

4. LOW SOCIAL STATUS

Most agricultural workers belong to the depressed classes, which have been neglected for 26 ages. The low caste and depressed classes have been socially handicapped and they had never the courage to assert themselves. They have been like dump-driven cattle. In some parts of India, agricultural

labourers are migratory, moving in search of jobs at the time of harvesting. Government measures to improve their lot by legislation have proved ineffective so far due to powerful hold of the rural elite classes in the rural economy.

5. DEMAND AND SUPPLY OF LABOUR

The number of agricultural labourers being very large and skills they possess being meager, there are generally more than abundant supply of agricultural labourer in relation to demand for them. It is only during the sowing and harvesting seasons that there appears to be nearfull employment in the case of agricultural labourers. But, once the harvesting season is over, majority of agricultural workers will be jobless especially in areas, where there is single cropping pattern.

6. LESS BARGAINING POWER

Due to all the above mentioned factors, the bargaining power and position of agricultural labourers in India is very weak. In fact, quite a large number of them are in the grip of village money lenders, landlords and commission agents, often the same person functioning in all the three capacities. No wonder, the agricultural labour is the most exploited class of people of India.

7. AT THE BIDDING OF THE LANDLORD

There is generally direct and day to day 'contact between agricultural labourers and the landlords' on whose farm they are working. Unlike industrial workers, this direct contact between the employer and employees is a distinct feature of agriculture labourer. The above mentioned few important characteristics distinguish agricultural labourers in India from industrial workers. Thus partly because of factors beyond their control and partly because of their inherent bargaining weakness, the farm labourers have been getting very low wages and have therefore to live in a miserable sub-human life.

8. AGRICULTURAL SERFS OR BONDED LABOURERS

At the bottom of the agricultural cadre in India are those labourers whose conditions are not very different from those of serfs. Agricultural serfdom has been most prevalent in those parts of India where the lower and the depressed classes and most in numerous. The ethnic composition of villages which governs the social stratification is responsible for the survival of the slavish conditions. In Gujarat, Maharashtra, Kerala, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Bihar, Orissa, Madhya Pradesh, a large aboriginal population live and the condition of this agricultural labours is very much like that of slaves. These are called in different names in different States.

HOW IMPORTANT ARE WOMEN TO AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION?

Economic integration has been strongly associated with increased employment of women in the paid, non-agricultural labour. Nevertheless, today, more than half of all women contribute to food production both for household production and sale. Women account for almost half of the world's agricultural workforce. They represent 47% in Africa, 17% in Latin America and the Caribbean and 44% of the regional agricultural workforce in Asia. However, women's role in agricultural production has been traditionally under-estimated and gender inequalities are pronounced in this sector. In developing countries, the great majority of women workers in agriculture are in subsistence farming, self-employed or working as unpaid family members.

OCCUPATIONAL HAZARDS IN AGRICULTURE

Official data on the incidence of occupational accidents and diseases are imprecise and notoriously underestimated, due to inadequate and heterogeneous recording and notifications systems. Furthermore, as only relatively few accidents are fatal and their notification mandatory, available information on workplace accidents does not reflect the very many nonfatal and minor injuries which fail to be reported. Even when an occupational injury is a cause of death, this fact is often missing from the death certificate. In the case of the agricultural sector under-reporting is even more evident. In many countries the reporting and compensation systems may exclude the agricultural sector or certain

categories of agricultural workers. Many countries group agriculture together with other sectors such as hunting, forestry and fishing in their global estimates.

Problems in diagnosis also lead to under-reporting in the vast majority of countries. Chronic conditions due to noise, vibration, and low exposure to dusts or pesticides are more difficult to evaluate due to their long-term effects and uncertain symptoms. Workers are thus deprived of proper treatment and appropriated preventive measures. This situation is becoming particularly serious with rapid technological changes in agricultural production and with an increasing use of hazardous substances. It is also amplified by the poor control that workers have over the rhythm, content and organization of their work and the weak enforcement of safety and health regulations in agricultural settings.

Characteristics of countries where agriculture contributed positively to poverty reduction

Agricultural progress contributes strongly to poverty reduction. Now we want to see if there are common characteristics of the agricultural economies of those countries where agriculture contributed positively to reducing poverty that might help us better understand what features of agricultural performance government's might wish to emphasize in their development efforts. Table 4 shows that agricultural GDP/worker grew, and thus contributed positively to poverty reduction, in twenty out of the twenty five countries.

AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY AND POVERTY

The payoff from investments in agricultural research, development, extension and education comes in the form of sustained increase in agricultural productivity. Comparisons of agricultural performance among countries and over time are frequently made using partial productivity indicators such as output, e.g. per unit of land, or head of livestock or agricultural worker. However these indicate only the trends in output relative to one input and can be misleading in cases where the input mix is changing or, especially, where there are technical advances allowing increases in output for a given level of input use.

A superior measure, frequently used to overcome these problems is total factor productivity (TFP). Thirtle, Lin and Piesse (2003) examine the impact of total factor productivity growth on the incidence of poverty in the LDCs, as measured by the percentage of the population living on less than USD 1.00 per day. Employing regression analysis their empirical analysis shows that agricultural productivity growth has a substantial impact on poverty reduction, whereas productivity growth in industry and services does not. They use their empirical findings to show that investment in agricultural R&D has had a substantial impact on poverty reduction in Africa and Asia, as well as paying for itself by being an extremely profitable investment. We should expect therefore that our selection of countries where agriculture contributed to extraordinary progress in poverty reduction might also have posted strong productivity gains. Fuglie (2008) reports findings from a comprehensive study of trends in total factor productivity covering 173 countries from 1961 to 2006. Figure 6 uses estimates taken from that analysis to compare performance of our selected countries and their respective regions. Notice that TFP growth rates were positive in all twenty of our chosen countries, with most averaging well above 1.6% per year which was the global average estimated by Fuglie for the range 1991-2006. Furthermore, more countries scored at or above their respective regional average than did not. Moreover, consistent with findings from Thirtle, Lin, and Piesse (2003) there is a strong correlation between rates of progress in TFP and in poverty reduction, *i.e.* those countries posting the fastest progress in TFP were generally those posting the fastest progress in reducing poverty. On the whole then it seems safe to conclude that agricultural TFP growth was a shared characteristic of the selected countries, undoubtedly contributing to poverty reduction

Measures taken by the Government to improve the Conditions of Agricultural Labourers :

The Government has shown awareness of the problems of agricultural workers and all plan documents have suggested ways and means to ameliorate the lot of these people. Measures adopted by the Government for ameliorating the economic conditions of Agricultural labourers are

1. Passing of minimum wage Act.
2. Abolition of Bonded Labourers

3. Providing land to landless labourers
4. Provision of Housing cities to houseless
5. Special schemes for providing employment
 - i) Crash Scheme for Rural Employment (CSRE)
 - ii) Pilot Intensive Rural Employment Project (PIREP)
 - iii) Food for works programme (FWP)
 - iv) National Rural Employment Programme (NREP)
 - v) Rural Landless Employment Programme (RLEP)
 - vi) Drought Prone Area Programme (It was known as Rural Works Programme)
6. Jawahar Rojgar Yojana (which come in with the merger of NREP and RLEGP)
7. Desert Development Programme
8. National Scheme of Training of Rural Youth for Self Employment (TRYSM)
9. Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA)
10. Abolition of Bonded Labourer Act
11. Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP)

Suggestions for the Improvement of Agricultural Labours :

The following suggestions can be made for the improvement of the socio-economic position of the agricultural labourers :

1. Better implementation of legislative measures.
2. Improvement the bargaining position.
3. Resettlement of agricultural workers
4. Creating alternative sources of employment
5. Protection of women and child labourers
6. Public works programmes should be for longer period in year
7. Improving the working conditions
8. Regulation of hours of work
9. Improvements in Agricultural sector
10. Credit at cheaper rates of interest on easy terms of payment for undertaking subsidiary occupation.
11. Proper training for improving the skill of farm labourers
12. Cooperative farming

CONCLUSION

In order to guarantee sustainable agricultural development in the new millennium, rural workers and their families should have access to adequate working and living conditions, health and welfare. An adequate balance between agricultural growth and the protection of the environment is also crucial for the future of the world's food production and for its sustainability. Occupational health in agriculture must be integrated into a rural development policy with a well-defined strategy. It should place an emphasis on prevention and environmental protection to be consistent with current trends and should be addressed both at national and international levels.

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MULTINATIONAL BUSINESS ARENA AND THE ROLE OF CORRUPTION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

Corruption in business occurs in situations of a quid pro quo relationship between public officials and business managers representing corporations. Many a time, such corrupt situations can harm stakeholder interests. Managers, as decision-makers, in corruption-related situations may fail to understand the impact of their decisions in such situation for they operate from a position of "position-dependent objectivity" focusing on economic objectives usually. Some corporations are willing to increase their profits through indulging in bribery, corruption and money-laundering, which has a tendency to degrade the governing system in the developing country. The paper seeks to explore and demonstrate the intensification of the role of MNCs in anti-social practices in a developing country, even though this role is in contradiction of the claims of MNCs to be socially responsible and accountable.

INTRODUCTION

Corruption in business is amongst the serious problems confronting global society today. United Nations, World Bank, OECD, and other international bodies acknowledge its occurrence in international business. However, corruption is not a recent phenomenon nor is it a creation of a particular society or civilization or present day business operations. The incidence of corruption was observed in all ancient civilizations.

Corruption continues to be a part of the contemporary social structures. We hear and read about the occurrence of corruption on a daily basis, in the media and the works of anticorruption bodies such as Transparency International. The phenomenon of corruption cuts across all cultures and continents. Corruption in business conduct is a sub-set of a wider phenomenon of corruption prevalent in all parts of the world.

Corruption in business usually occurs during the interface between business managers and public officials. Business managers seek dispensation of favours (both legitimate and illegitimate) and public officials command the discretion to dispense those favours.

There are several types of corruption. The distinctions can be useful in designing and developing reform programs and strategies:

- 1. Petty corruption** - practiced by public servants who may be basically decent and honest individuals but who are grossly underpaid and depend on small bribes from the public to feed and educate their families;
- 2. Grand corruption** - high-level public officials and politicians make decisions involving large public contracts or projects financed by external donors. This corruption is motivated by personal greed. The money or assets from such corruption usually is transferred to individuals or political party coffers.
- 3. Episodic corruption** - honest behaviour is the norm, corruption the exception, and the dishonest public servant is disciplined when detected; and

4. Systemic corruption - channels of malfeasance extend upwards from the bribe collection points, and systems depend on corruption for their survival;

Corruption can also be categorized in other ways. A distinction can be made between benefits that are paid willingly (bribery) and payments that are exacted from unwilling clients (extortion). Another way to categorize is to differentiate between bribes paid for what a client has a legal right to receive and bribes paid to receive benefits belonging to others.

MULTINATIONAL BUSINESS AND ROLE OF CORRUPTION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

Current approaches from the organization for economic co-operation and development, the World Bank, and furthers on the issue of bribery have taken extensive concentration. Though, this is found that the occurrence of corruption is directly related with, recognitions and privatization where MNCs depended in organization for economic co-operation and development nations place to increase gainful trade.

The support of privatization through the World Bank, and the financial advantage to organization for economic co-operation and development MNCs from this trade, signify that activity alongside bribery requires to engage successful permits through growing nations against MNCs which involve in dishonest efforts; better political clearness to eradicate the confidentiality below which bribery increases; and confrontation to the unsuspecting expansion of privatization. Bribery takes several diverse shapes, from the regular matters of corruption otherwise minor exploitation of authority that is said to 'oil the structure', by to the growth of impressive individual prosperity whether by misuse otherwise by more corrupt indicates.

corporations is able to increase superior incomes: also through attractive agreements otherwise allowances which they would not or else have succeed, otherwise through achieving deals otherwise allowances on further favourable, and thus extra gainful, conditions. This creates it a grave difficulty for public powers and the community. Primary, as it creates the facility for extra expensive than it would be or else. Next, as it distorts autonomous procedures and normal decision-taking process.

EFFECTS OF CORRUPTION IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

Reality in many developing countries today is still shaped like this: relatively underdeveloped public institutions, small upper class elites, and huge differences in wealth and income-with the concomitant possibilities of wielding power and exercising authority. Under these conditions corruption has especially deplorable effects. Where it spreads no bedrock remains in the long run; habituation to dishonesty destroys all sense of honesty. The disposition to corrupt and be corrupted rather than qualifications comes to determine relations between people. Corrupt conduct in office ends up as flagrant disregarding of community interests.

The ones short-changed by all this are the socially powerless and decent people, for they either cannot or will not join in playing the crooked game. Because of their poverty or uprightness they constantly get short shrift in comparison with those who have the wherewithal to influence decisions and the way things are handled to their advantage and are not shy about doing so.

When it comes down to cases this often means that quite normal services to which all citizens are nominally entitled by the constitution and the law are denied persons from the underclass, already under severe social duress, unless they cough up. It starts with giving someone who needs a certificate of birth or death a hard time, continues where children are enrolled in school, testimonials are required for job applications or positions with government are filled, and does not stop even when, following a catastrophe, the state distributes free or subsidized relief goods such as food.

Those, on the other hand, who thanks to their connections and social status and the pull these confer, are better off and in a position to dispense pecuniary or other favors need not fear mistreatment.

Oftentimes they do not even have to pay their full taxes or other levies. Thus privileged, they regularly enjoy the benefits of government-provided services that, in view of their social position, they ought not and certainly have no need to profit from.

PREVENTION: AN IMPORTANT TOOL IN FIGHTING CORRUPTION

Corruption is viewed as a systemic issue requiring the donors to work on several fronts and to collaborate with all branches of government and many parts of society. The approach to promote good governance through among other things, prevention, is to help client countries curb corruption and build integrity, and therefore, improve their public services and create an enabling environment for the private sector. The Governance and Anti-Corruption program comprises three principal activity areas:

- (a) improving public sector service delivery by focusing on public sector accountability and legal reform in order to re-introduce rule of law;
- (b) building integrity by promoting governmental accountability and transparency; and
- (c) building an prevention and anti-corruption capacity of the public sector-including parliament, watchdog and enforcement agencies, and the judiciary-and of civil society, particularly by strengthening non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and the media.

CONCLUSION

Although corruption exists in all countries it is more widespread in low income countries. This is not because people in poor countries are more corruptible than their counterparts in rich countries. It is simply because conditions in poor countries are more conducive for the growth of corruption.

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A STUDY ON STATUS OF AWARENESS AMONG MUTUAL FUND INVESTORS IN TAMILNADU

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ABSTRACT

Mutual funds have become an important intermediary between households and financial markets, particularly the equity market. By providing liquid, low cost shares in a diversified portfolio of financial assets selected by professional money managers, mutual funds have enabled an increasing number of households to enter financial markets and the diversified investment structure of mutual funds and diversified risk contributed tremendously in the growth of mutual funds. It is important to study the awareness of mutual fund among the investors.

INTRODUCTION

The Indian capital market has grown so sharply in the 80's that the decade itself has been christened as a decade of the capital market. More particularly, during the later part of the eighties, the primary and the secondary markets have grown by leaps and bounds. The increasing volatility in the market has also motivated the investors to invest in another relatively safe vehicle of investment. Earlier investors used to invest directly in the stock market and many times suffered from loss due to wrong speculation. But in the recent days most of the investors preferred to invest their funds on mutual funds. A lot of variants to standard mutual funds have come and the investment companies continually introduced new types of investment schemes in an effort to attract investor's capital and maximize assets under management.

Since 1990, total mutual fund assets have increased nearly sevenfold, and the assets of mutual funds that invest in stocks have grown even more, expanding nearly twentyfold. Over the same period, mutual fund assets have come to account for a larger share of household wealth. Moreover, a greater proportion of Indian households now own stock, in large part because of their investments in mutual funds. Much of this growth has come in households' retirement assets, as developments in pension plans and other tax preferred retirement accounts have increasingly made it possible for households to control more of their retirement asset portfolios and households have tended to invest a significant portion of their retirement assets in mutual funds.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Stock market plays a very vital role in developing economy in India. It is also attracting the many people in recent years. Investors usually perceive that all capital market investment avenues are risky. Based on objectives and risk bearing capacities, investors go for different investment alternatives. Among the various investment possibilities, mutual fund (MF) seems to be viable for all kind of investors as it is considered to be a safer mode of investment. As the mutual fund industry provides an option of diversified investment structure with varying degree of risk, it was supposed to be the most lucrative market for Indian investors.

It was believed that as against the developed countries where almost every second investor is a mutual unit holder, the product could not get much popularity in India. As of now big challenge for the MF industry is to mount on investor awareness and to spread further to the semi-urban and rural areas. These initiatives would help towards making the MF industry more vibrant and competitive. Since, the need of study has been aroused in order to see the preference, awareness and the investors' perception regarding the mutual funds in Tamilnadu, this study is an eye-opener, not just for marketers of mutual funds but also for policy and decision-makers in the government.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The investors who invest in growth or equity schemes consider it as an alternative to stock market investing and the investors who invest in debt schemes expect higher returns on their investments than returns on nationalized banks' fixed deposits. The investors expect higher returns and get dissatisfied when they don't receive the expected returns. The NAV of the mutual fund scheme gets discounted on debiting the front-ended load of issue expenses after closure, further discounted on listing and continue to decline on trading due to poor demand for such units due to the poor sentiments of the investors. Another one biggest risk of investing in a mutual fund is one of underperformance. When an investor decides to invest in a particular asset class, he typically expects to get the return that the benchmark of the asset provides. Mutual funds try to maximise the returns on the funds invested through them but all of the funds cannot succeed an outperforming each other or the benchmark.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study was based on the following objectives

1. To analyze the investors awareness regarding mutual fund investment
2. To measure the investors' level of satisfaction towards mutual fund investment

Hypothesis

Based on the objectives, the followings null hypothesis was framed for this study:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between demographic characteristics of the respondents and their level of awareness about mutual fund investments.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study is descriptive in nature. The present study attempts to evaluate the investor's awareness and satisfaction towards the mutual fund investments. For the purpose, individual mutual funds investors have been selected. The individual investors' awareness and satisfaction has been confined to the only selected districts of Tamil Nadu.

SAMPLING DESIGN

The sample size covered 500 investors of Tamil Nadu who were spread through five different districts namely Cuddalore, Coimbatore, Chennai, Madurai and Trichy districts of Tamil Nadu. These districts where large numbers of MFs investors are available are identified for this study using Purposive Sampling Method. In order to collect referred information from the retail investors, the sampling design was carefully decided and properly chosen for the study. From each identified districts, five approved brokers of were chosen and twenty MF investors were contacted with the help of brokers. Thus, this study was based on the responses by 500 selected respondents.

COLLECTION OF DATA

The researcher was used survey method for data collection. This study gathered the desired data through primary sources. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire from the retail investors living in selected districts of Tamil Nadu and invested in MF schemes.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The researcher collected the required primary data from the selected respondents during period from June 2012 to Dec. 2012.

TOOLS FOR ANALYSIS

The collected primary data were analyzed by applying various statistical tools such as descriptive statistics like simple percentages, cross-tabulation, and Chi-square tests have been used. The chi-square test has been adopted to examine the association between the personal and family factors with the level of awareness.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table - 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Personal Variables		No. of Respondents	%
Gender	Male	357	71.40
	Female	143	28.60
Age (in years)	Up to 30	58	11.60
	31- 40	145	29.00
	41-50	210	42.00
	Above 50	87	17.40
Education status	School Final	54	10.80
	Graduate	124	24.80
	Post Graduate	197	39.40
	Professional degree	81	16.20
	Diploma and others	44	8.80
Monthly Family Income (in Rs)	Upto 10000	79	15.80
	10001-20000	191	38.20
	20001-30000	169	33.80
	Above 30000	61	12.20
Occupation	Salaried	198	39.60
	Business	127	25.40
	Professionals	56	11.20
	Agriculturalist	34	6.80
	Retired	62	12.40
	Self employed and others	23	4.60
Family pattern	Nuclear family	348	69.60
	Joint family	152	30.40
Residence	Rural	129	25.80
	Semi urban	235	47.00
	Urban	136	27.20
Size of Family Members	1-2	77	15.40
	3-4	158	31.60
	5-6	179	35.80
	7 and above	86	17.20
Earning Members	One	156	31.20
	Two	198	39.60
	Three	79	15.80
	Four and above	67	13.40
	Total	500	100

Source: Primary Data.

Out of 500 respondents, 71.40 per cent are male and 28.60 per cent are female. The predominant age group of the respondents (42 per cent) in respondents groups is 41-50 years. A good majority of the remaining respondents are dispersed in the age group 31-40 years and above 50 years. 4.15 per cent of the respondents are dispersed in the age group of above 55 years. The predominant literacy group (39.40 per cent) of the respondents has post graduate. 24.80 per cent of the respondents have graduate qualifications. 16.20 per cent and 10.80 per cent of the respondents have studied professional degree and school final respectively. Majority of the respondents (38.20 per cent) have a monthly income in the range Rs. 10001-20000, and 33.80 per cent of the respondents have Rs. 20001-30000 as monthly income. 15.80 % and 12.20 per cent of the respondents have monthly income in the range upto Rs.10000 and above Rs.30000 respectively.

Out of 500 respondents, 39.60 per cent are employed, 25.40 per cent are business man, 11.20 per cent of the respondents are professionals, 12.40 per cent are retired persons and 6.80 per cent are agriculturalist. As regards to family pattern 69.60 per cent of the respondents are from nuclear family, 30.40 per cent are from joint family. As regards to area of residence, 25.80 per cent of the respondents are from rural, 47 per cent are from semi urban and 27.20 per cent of the respondents from urban area. 35.80

per cent of the respondents have 5 to 6 family members, about 31.60 per cent have 3 to 4 dependants, 15.40 per cent have 1 to 2 dependants, and 17.20 per cent of the respondents have 7 and above dependants. 39.60 per cent of the respondents have 2 earning members in their family, about 31.20 per cent of the respondents have only one earning member and 15.80 have 3 earning members, 13.40 per cent have 4 and more earning members in their family.

AWARENESS OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the competitive environment, the investees are providing a lot of features to customers. At the same time, the level of awareness of the investors is not up to the mark. Against this background, in this section an attempt has been made to investigate status of awareness among mutual fund investors about various types and schemes of mutual funds in the study area and the results of the evaluation are reported in Table 2

Table 2 Status of Awareness among Mutual Fund Investors

Sl. No.	Variables	Fully Aware		Somewhat Aware		Doubtful		Not Aware		Not at all aware	
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	Rate of return	197	39.4	142	28.4	64	12.8	55	11.0	42	8.4
2	Liquidity	114	22.8	159	31.8	58	11.6	87	17.4	82	16.4
3	Safety and security	188	37.6	131	26.2	54	10.8	76	15.2	51	10.2
4	Tax Benefits	225	45.0	142	28.4	47	9.4	49	9.8	37	7.4
5	Capital gain	178	35.6	128	25.6	61	12.2	103	20.6	30	6.0
6	Growth prospects	69	13.8	98	19.6	57	11.4	164	32.8	112	22.4
7	Maturity period	172	34.4	136	27.2	94	18.8	53	10.6	45	9.0
8	Sources of information	219	43.8	133	26.6	52	10.4	62	12.4	34	6.8
9	Rules and regulations	186	37.2	115	23.0	65	13.0	84	16.8	50	10.0
10	Variety and schemes	201	40.2	129	25.8	72	14.4	52	10.4	46	9.2
11	Grievance handling	128	25.6	69	12.8	41	8.2	159	31.8	103	20.6
12	Options available	231	46.2	128	25.6	69	13.8	49	9.8	23	4.6
13	Fund Performance and Reputation	131	26.2	103	20.6	45	9.0	124	24.8	97	19.4
14	Risks in investment	239	47.8	185	37.0	26	5.2	32	6.4	18	3.6
15	Expert Guidance	89	17.8	72	14.4	32	6.4	149	29.8	158	31.6
16	Minimum capital required	229	45.8	146	29.2	42	8.4	62	12.4	21	4.2
17	Investor services	167	33.4	116	23.2	53	10.6	105	21.0	59	11.8
18	Sponsors' reputation	206	41.2	172	34.4	42	8.4	47	9.4	33	6.6
19	Disclosure of NAV	114	22.8	92	18.4	58	11.6	146	29.2	90	18.0
20	Rating given	136	27.2	124	24.8	78	15.6	71	14.2	91	18.2
21	Skills of Fund Managers	92	18.4	83	16.6	65	13.0	152	30.4	108	21.6
22	Available Diversification	131	26.2	135	27.0	61	12.2	92	18.4	81	16.2

Source: Primary data

The researcher has aggregated the fully aware and somewhat aware as aware and also aggregates the not aware & not at all aware, as not aware. It is observed from the Table -2 that more than half of the MF investors are found to be aware of Rate of return (67.8 %), Liquidity (54.6%), safety and security (63.8%), tax benefits (73.4%), capital gain (61.2%), maturity period (61.6%), sources of information (70.4%), rules and regulations (60.2%), variety and schemes (66 %), options available (71.8%), fund performance and reputation (46.8%), risks in investment(84.8%), minimum capital required (75%), investor services (56.6%), sponsors' reputation (75.6%), rating given (52%) and available diversification (53.2%). More number of investors is not aware about growth prospects (55.2%), grievance handling (52.4%), expert guidance (61.4%), disclosure of NAV (47.2%) and skills of fund managers (52%).

QUANTIFICATION OF DATA TO MEASURE THE AWARENESS LEVEL

A list of 22 statements relating to mutual fund investment is constructed. In this present study, the level of awareness has been measured with the help of scaling technique developed by researcher. The five point scale is used. 5 points have been assigned for fully aware, four points for somewhat aware, three points for Doubtful, two points for not aware and one point has been assigned for not at all aware. By adding scores, the extent of level of awareness has been measured.

Suppose a respondent has chosen 'Fully aware' for all the twenty two components, he/she will be given 110 score at the rate of five score for each component. Suppose the respondent chooses 'to somewhat aware' for all the twenty two components, he/she will be given 88 score at the rate of four score for each component. If the choice of the respondents for all the twenty two components is 'not at all aware,' he/she will get a score of 22 at the rate of one score for each component. Therefore the total maximum and minimum score would be 55,000 (110 x 500) and 11,000 (22 x 500) respectively.

LEVEL OF AWARENESS

The mean and standard deviation (SD) of the total awareness score of 500 respondents are computed. If the scores above (Mean + SD) are considered to be of high level of awareness, if scores below (Mean - SD) are treated as low level of awareness and the total scores between (Mean + SD) and (Means- SD) are treated as medium level of awareness. The total score is 46,640, Mean score is 93.28 and SD is 5.93. The respondents with awareness score above 99.21 (Mean + SD) are considered to be having high awareness, respondents with awareness score below 87.35 (Mean - SD) are considered to be having low awareness and the respondents whose awareness score is between 87.35 and 99.21 are assumed to be having medium levels of awareness about mutual fund and its' features. The different levels of awareness of the respondents are given in the following Table 3.

Table - 3 Respondents' Level of Awareness about Mutual Funds

Sl. No.	Level of Awareness	Total
1	High	289 (57.8)
2	Medium	174 (34.8)
3	Low	37 (7.4)
	Total	500

Source: Computed

It is seen from the Table 3 that out of 500 respondents, 289 have high awareness about MF investment. They occupy the largest proportion of the sample respondents. The respondents with medium level of awareness are 174 (34.8%) and the respondents with the low level of awareness are 37 (7.4%).

Association between Demographic Profile and Level of Awareness of the Respondents

The association between the profile of the respondents and their awareness on mutual funds and its features has been examined with the help of chi-square test. In order to measure the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and level of awareness of the respondents, the researcher has

framed the following null hypothesis: "There is no significant association between the personal variables of respondents (such as age, gender, marital status, educational qualification, occupation, size of family, monthly income) and their awareness level on mutual fund investments.

Table 4 Investors' Satisfaction on Mutual fund investment

Factors	Level of Satisfaction (%)			Total
	Fully	Partly	Dissatisfi	
With Rate of return	56	32	12	100
With Liquidity	43	27	30	100
With Safety and security	62	29	9	100
With Tax Benefits	56	34	10	100
With Capital gain	42	24	34	100
With Growth prospects	34	21	45	100
With Maturity period	53	18	29	100
With Sources of information	68	21	11	100
With Rules and regulations	47	9	44	100
With Variety and schemes	55	19	26	100
With Grievance handling	34	13	53	100
With Options available	59	26	15	100
With Risks in investment	23	14	63	100
With Investor services	34	20	46	100
With Rating given	32	16	52	100
With Diversification	47	21	32	100
With Skills of Fund Managers	51	15	34	100
Overall	61	22	17	100

Source: Computed from primary data

It is observed from Table 5 that out of the 500 respondents, 61 % of the respondents were satisfied, 22% of the respondents were partially satisfied and 17 % of the respondents were dissatisfied with the investment in MFs in Tamil Nadu. It also reveals from the above table that out of the 500 sample respondents, 56%, 32 % and 12 % of the respondents were satisfied, partially satisfied and dissatisfied with rate of return from mutual funds.

Out of 500 sample respondents 62 per cent satisfied with safety and security, 56 per cent satisfied with tax benefits, 42 per cent satisfied with capital gain, 53 per cent satisfied with maturity period, 68 per cent satisfied with sources of information, 47 per cent satisfied with rules and regulations, 55 per cent satisfied with variety and schemes, 59 per cent satisfied with options available, 47 per cent satisfied with diversification, 51 per cent satisfied with skills of fund managers. Further, from Table --- it is observed that out of the 500 respondents, 45 per cent dissatisfied with growth prospects, 53 per cent dissatisfied with grievance handling, 63 per cent dissatisfied with risks in investment, 46 per cent dissatisfied with investor services and 52 per cent dissatisfied with rating given.

CONCLUSION

This study is very important in order to judge the investors' behaviour in a market like India, where the competition increases day by day due to the entry of large number of players with different financial strengths and strategies. The present study analyses the MF investments in relation to investor's level of awareness and satisfaction has been studied relating to various issues like factors that attract them to invest in mutual funds, rate of return, liquidity, safety and security, tax consideration, capital gain, growth prospects, role of financial advisors and brokers, maturity period, market information, rules and regulations and variety and schemes, deficiencies in the services provided by the mutual fund managers, challenges before the Indian mutual fund industry etc. The present investigation outlined that mostly the investors have high level awareness and positive approach towards investing in MF.

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A STUDY ON ROSE CULTIVATION AND MARKETING PATTERN IN HOSUR TALUK

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INTRODUCTION

Flowers are inseparable from the social fabric of human life. Flowers being adorable Creation of God befits all occasions be it at birth, marriage or death. In the past, flowers were not of much economic importance. One would grow flowers to fulfill his or her aesthetic desire. At times, flowers were offered for sale to meet the special requirements of people. With the passage of time drastic changes have come about in the life style of people leading to commercialized cultivation of flowers. Today, flower plants are no longer meant for only window garden but play an important role in the decoration of the living houses and office establishments. Floriculture is a fast emerging and highly competitive industry. With the continuous introduction of new cultivators and new crops, cultural techniques are changing and hence new products are developing. Ornamental crop culture technology is improving with the availability of equipment and there is a sea change in the trend of consumers. A new generation of growers is coming forward to employ modern technology for maximizing production and offer quality produce for consumer acceptability, thus fetching a better price.

PRESENT SITUATION OF ROSE CULTIVATION

In spite of the long and close association with floriculture, the records of commercial activity in the field are very few. The information on the area under floriculture and the production generated is highly inadequate. As commercial floriculture is an activity which has assumed importance only in recent times, there are not many large farms engaged in organized floriculture. In most part of the country flower growing is carried out on small holdings, mainly as a part of the regular agriculture systems.

RESEARCH SUPPORT

Research work on floriculture is being carried out at several research institutions under the Indian Council of Agricultural Research and Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, in the horticulture/floriculture departments of State Agricultural Universities and under the All India Coordinated Floriculture Improvement Project with a network of about twenty (20) centres. The crops which have received larger attention include rose, gladiolus, chrysanthemum, orchid, jasmine, tuberose, aster, marigold etc. The thrust till recently had been on crop improvement, standardization of agro-techniques including improved propagation methods, plant protection and post harvest management. In view of the fact that most of the cut flower production is being done under open field conditions, the research efforts generally relate to open cultivation. In recent years, however, technologies for protected cultivation and tissue culture for mass propagation have also received attention. A large number of varieties suitable for cut flower use, as well as garden display have been developed. Production technology, particularly the agronomic requirements and control methods for important diseases and insect pests have also been developed. Contribution by the private sector in research activities in floriculture is negligible.

MARKETING

Marketing of cut flowers in India is very unorganized at present. In most metropolitan cities, with large market potential, flowers are brought to wholesale markets, which mostly operate in open yards. A few large flower merchants generally buy most of the produce and distribute them to local retail outlets after significant mark up. The retail florist shops also usually operate in the open on-road sides, with different flowers arranged in large buckets. In the metros, however, there are some good florist show rooms, where flowers are kept in controlled temperature conditions, with considerable attention to value added service. The government is now investing in setting up of auction platforms, as well as organized florist shops with better storage facilities to prolong shelf life.

The packaging and transportation of flowers from the production centres to the wholesale markets at present is very unscientific. The flowers, depending on the kind, are packed in old gunny bags, bamboo baskets, simple cartons or just wrapped in old newspapers and transported to markets by road, rail or by air. The mode of transportation depends on the distance to the markets and the volume. Mostly, flowers are harvested in the evening time and transported to nearby cities by overnight trains or buses. In recent years, the government has provided some assistance for buying refrigerated carriage vans. A large number of export oriented units have built up excellent facilities of pre-cooling chambers, cold stores and reefer vans and their produce coming for domestic market sales are thus of very good quality and have longer vase life and command higher price. The government programmes for floriculture development include creating common facilities of cool chain in large production areas to be shared on cooperative basis. Formations of growers' cooperatives/associations are being encouraged.

In view of the unorganized set up, it is difficult to estimate the size of flower trade, both in terms of volume and value. A study conducted in 1989 estimated the trade to be worth Rs. 2050 million. It is in the period of the last five years or so that this business has really boomed in India, which is reflected in the number of new florist outlets in all cities and increase in the public's purchase of flowers as gifts. This would put the current trade at several times the earlier estimate. A recent study of Delhi market alone put the value of flowers traded on wholesale as Rs. 500 million.

The loose flowers (traditional crops like marigold, jasmine etc.) are usually traded by weight. The average price of different flowers in major markets varies considerably depending on the period of availability (Table 1.1).

INDIAN SCENARIO AND TRADE

India is bestowed with diverse agro-climatic and ecological conditions, which are favorable to grow all types of commercially important flowers generally found in different parts of the world. It also enjoys the best climate in selected pockets for floriculture during winter months. India is in an enviable position to become a leader in the world floricultural trade because of the prevailing congenial location, overall favorable climate of liberalization and globalization and also specific incentives by the government and floricultural development. Specific and authentic quantitative data are not available for existing production and area under floriculture in India. According to the horticulture production year book 2001 of national horticultural board, an area of 88,600 ha during 1999-2000 was under floriculture in India with production of 5.09 lakh MT of loose flowers and 680.6 million numbers of cut flowers. Loose flowers were grown in 73,536 ha of land. Flowers are grown under open cultivation and also under protected cultivation. In the polyhouses, mainly roses are grown for export. Other exotic flowers like carnations, rose, orchids, liliun and other bulbous flowers are now increasingly produced commercially both for export and domestic market. Floricultural exports from India during 1997-98 was Rs. 81.20 crore, Rs. 96.60 crore in 1998-99, Rs. 105.15 crore in 1999-2000 and Rs. 190.63 crore in 2000-01. In spite of this increase in India exports, its share in the international flower trade has not increased during 1995 to 2000 and has remained at around 0.35 per cent. The main importing countries of Indian floricultural products in order are The Netherlands, USA, Japan, Germany, Italy, Denmark, Egypt, Singapore, Switzerland, France, Australia, UAE, Belgium and Sri lanka. During the year 1999-2000, Indian floricultural products were exported to 75 different countries.

STATUS OF FLORICULTURE IN HOSUR TALUK

Hosur is a leading area and production of rose flowers in the country. The area under flower crops was 20,801 ha and the production was 1.24 lakhs million tones of loose flowers during 2011-2012. A large number of flowers like jasmine, tuberose, rose, chrysanthemum, marigold, crossandra, barleria, lily, limonium, alsteoemeria, liatris, freesia, iris, lisianthus, calla, carnation, rose and anthurium are commercially cultivated in the state. Many hi-tech units with export tie-ups are there in the Karnataka state. There are several commercial tissue culture laboratories. The daily average trade of cut flower is over Rs. 2 lakh and loose flower over Rs. 5 lakh in Hosur itself.

Area under rose cultivation in Hosur Taluk is estimated at 25 ha with production of 53 lakhs cut flowers at an estimated value of Rs. 15 lakh. In recent years the area under rose and carnation is fast increasing around Hosur Taluk and Bangalore because of high profits. As far as the productivity is

concerned there is a lot of scope for increasing the productivity and profit through adoption of the latest improved production and marketing technologies. There is a need to generate information regarding production and marketing aspects, the profile of cut flower growers and the constraints in production and marketing of cut flowers. Therefore, a study of this nature was very much required to understand and obtain suitable feedback which will be useful to cut flower growers, extension workers, scientists, administrators and planners. Hence, the study was conducted with the following objectives;

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Cut flower (rose and carnation) cultivation is highly profitable in India compared to other countries in the world and more so in Hosur Taluk. There is bright prospect for the expansion of area under cut flowers in the coming years. Therefore, it is pertinent and appropriate to study the knowledge level, adoption level and marketing problems of these crops, since there are no scientific enquiries in these aspects. The results will be useful to all the concerned for developing strategies to increase area, productivity of crop, profit and export earnings.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the knowledge and adoption of recommended cultivation practices of rose Flowers by farmers.
2. To study the marketing pattern of rose flowers by farmers
3. To study the profile of rose flower growers
4. To find out the factors motivating the farmers to grow rose flowers
5. To identify the constraints in cultivation and marketing of rose flowers

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Due to limitation of time and other reasons, the study was restricted to Hosur Taluk. Generalization of result may not be possible for different cut flower growing areas. Further, the findings of the study were based on the responses of the respondents and hence the objectivity is limited to the honesty and memory power of the respondents.

METHODOLOGY : The study was conducted in the Hosur Taluk of Krishnagiri district in Tamil Nadu. This area deals about the material and methodology followed in conducting the research under the following sub headings.

1. LOCALE OF THE STUDY: In Tamil Nadu state, Hosur is having maximum area under Rose cultivation and ranks first in area and production. The growers are scattered throughout the Hosur Taluk. So, the areas Berikai, Bagalur, Zeemangalam, Dasarapalli, Udanapalli, Swanipura, Eluvapalli, Karapalli, was selected purposively as locale of the study.

2 Selection of Respondents: In Hosur taluk, a list of one hundred farmers cultivating Rose flowers was selected for the present study.

3 Marketing pattern followed by the Respondents: The marketing pattern of the respondents was studied by asking them to indicate then nature of marketing, which included where, when, to whom and through which channel, they sell their produce of Rose flowers. Responses obtained from the farmers were expressed in frequencies and percentages.

.4 Constraints faced by the Respondents: The constraints faced in cultivation and marketing of Rose flowers by the farmers of the study area were listed out during pre-test and also in consultation with the extension personnel of State Department of Horticulture. Based on the responses obtained from the Rose growers, frequency and percentages were calculated for each constraint faced by the growers.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Karpagam (2008) conducted a study on turmeric growers in Erode district of Tamil Nadu state and found that, majority (70.00 per cent) of respondents had medium level of knowledge about turmeric cultivation practices followed by high (20.83 per cent) and low (9.17 per cent) knowledge respectively.

Kubde *et al.* (2000) in their study on knowledge and adoption of cultivation and storage protection of potato in Pune district of Maharashtra revealed that, majority of the potato growers had complete knowledge about recommended varieties (100 per cent), time of sowing (95.50 per cent), soil type required for cultivation of potato (79.00 per cent), seed rate (67.50 per cent), name of pests of potato and their control measures (54.00 per cent).

Kubde *et al.* (2008) in their study in Pune district of Maharashtra reported that, the potato growers had partially adopted recommended spacing (97 per cent), plant protection measures (82.0 per cent) manures (64.5 per cent) and fertilizers (55.5 per cent).

Babanna (2009) in his study on training needs of arecanut farmers in Shimoga district of Karnataka reported that, 35 per cent of the respondents belonged to medium adoption category followed by 33.4 per cent and 31.6 per cent of the respondents belonging to high and low adoption category.

Vedamurthy (2009) in his study on arecanut growers of Shimoga district reported that, majority of the arecanut growers adopted cultural practices (90.66 per cent) while 68.00 per cent of the growers adopted age of the seedlings, 73.00 per cent adopted the advocated spacing and 59.33 per cent of growers fully adopted the recommended practices of harvesting and processing. To summarize, most of the studies reported that, majority of the farmers had medium level of adoption of cultivation practices.

Shashidhara (2010) in his study on socio-economic profile of drip irrigation farmers in Shimoga and Davanagere district of Karnataka state revealed that, comparatively more number of farmers (46.67 per cent) belonged to semi medium category followed by medium (32.22 per cent) and small land holding categories (18.89 per cent). From the above studies, it could be concluded that, majority of farmers had semi medium land holding.

Shashidhara (2010) conducted a study on drip irrigation farmers in Bijapur district of Karnataka and reported that, 49.17 per cent of the farmers belonged to medium income category followed by low (26.67 per cent) and high (24.16 per cent) income category, respectively. The above studies revealed that, majority of farmers belonged to medium income category followed by low income category.

Natikar (2011) in his study on attitude and use of farm journals by the farmers found out that, majority of the respondents (65.0 per cent) had medium economic motivation. While 18.75 per cent and 16.25 per cent of the respondent's belonged to high and low level of economic motivation, respectively.

Natikar (2011) conducted a study on attitude and use of farm journal by the subscriber farmers and their profile North Karnataka and revealed that, 73.75 per cent of the subscriber farmers belonged to medium innovativeness category followed by low (15.63 per cent) and high (10.62 per cent) innovativeness categories.

Shashidhara (2011) in his study on socio-economic profile of drip irrigation farmers in Shimoga and Davanagere district of Karnataka found out that, majority of the farmers belonged to medium innovativeness category (47.50 per cent) followed by low (31.66 per cent) and high (20.83 per cent) innovativeness category, respectively.

Dhamodaran and Vasanthakumar (2012) in their study on adoption of improved sugarcane cultivation practices revealed that, majority of the respondents (52.50 per cent) had low level of extension agency contact, followed by 47.50 per cent of the respondents had medium level of extension agency contact.

Sunilkumar (2012) revealed that, 40.83 per cent of the respondents belonged to medium extension contact category followed by 30.00 per cent and 29.16 per cent belonging to high and low categories of extension contact, in Belgaum district of Karnataka state, respectively.

Sunilkumar (2012) revealed that, nearly 23.00 per cent of respondents participated regularly in agricultural exhibition followed by 20.83 per cent in demonstrations. Majority of them never attended in activities like training (66.67 per cent), educational tour (94.17 per cent) and field visits (92.05 per cent).

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 7.3 SHOWING NATURE OF MARKETING.

SL.NO	Particulars	No. of respondents
1.	Direct marketing	42
2.	Local retailer	54
3.	Commission agents	4
4.	Others	-
	Total	100

Data source: Primary data

From the above table 7.3 shows that the 42% of the respondents are involved direct marketing, 54% of the respondents are depend on local retailers and 4% of the respondents are depend commission agents.

TABLE 7.4 SHOWING THE PRODUCTION PROBLEMS

SL.NO	Particulars	No of respondents
1.	Problem of pests	8
2.	Problem of diseases	10
3.	High cost of fertilizers	16
4.	High cost of plant protection chemicals	8
5.	Limited &irregularity of power supply	28
6.	High investment in establishing a polyhouse	20
7.	All the above	10
	Total	100

Data source: Primary source

From the above table 7.4 shows that the 8% of the respondents are affected the problem of pests, 10% of the respondents are affected problem of diseases, 16% of the respondents are affected with high cost of fertilizers, 8% of the respondents are affected with high cost of plant protection chemicals, 28% of the respondents have only limited & irregularity of power supply, 20% of the respondents are highly invested in a polyhouse and 10% of the respondents faced all the above problems.

TABLE 7.5 SHOWING THE MARKETING PROBLEMS

SL.NO	Particulars	No of respondents
1.	Poor transportation facilities	4
2.	Low price for the flowers	28
3.	Fluctuations in the price	40
4.	Exploitation by the middleman	24
5.	Lack of exclusive markets for flowers	-
6.	Lack of storage facilities	2
7.	All the above	2
	Total	100

Data source: Primary source

From the above table 4.10.1 shows that the 4% of the respondents are affected poor transportation facilities, 28% of the respondents are faced by low price for the flowers, 40% of the respondents problem faced by fluctuations in the prices, 2% of the respondents exploitation by the middle man, 24% of the respondents are problem faced by the lack of storage facilities and 2% of the respondents are faced all the problems.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

New technology in agriculture has widened the horizons of productivity contours of various crops. Now-a-days there is a shift towards commercialization of agriculture and farmers are giving importance to commercial crops rather than other food crops. Floriculture is one such commercial field, which yields more income to the farmers.

Rose and carnation are important commercial cut flower crops grown in Karnataka particularly around big towns and cities. The area is increasing every year in view of high profit, good market and favorable agro climatic condition congenial for the crop. Large number of traditional farmers have switched over to cultivation of these cut flowers.

In spite of all its advantages, cultivation has not spread over to all parts of Karnataka. Hardly any research pertaining to these crops has been done and it was felt that the findings with respect to the level of knowledge and adoption regarding the recommended cultivation practices and constraints faced by the farmers would focus light on those area where the cultivators were found to be lacking. This will also enable the Horticulture Department in planning appropriate strategies to rejuvenate cut flowers cultivation.

The present study was conducted during the year 2012-2013 in Hosur Taluk. 100 rose cultivators were selected for the study, which constituted the total sample of 100 rose flower growers. The Krishnagiri district was purposively selected as it ranks first in area and production of cut flowers in Hosur taluk. The data was collected by using structured interview schedule developed for the study. The data was analyzed by using frequency and percentage.

THE MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE STUDY ARE AS FOLLOWS

- Forty per cent of rose growers possessed high level of knowledge about recommended cultivation practices
- Forty per cent of rose growers belonged to medium adoption category.
- Cent per cent of rose growers had knowledge about soil sterilization practice, digging of trench, use of suitable soil, type of bed preparation, use of planting material, spacing between row and plants, raking of soil, removal of old leaves, leaves to be retained, removal of suckers, pest and diseases and harvesting of flowers and treatment of flowers
- Cent per cent of carnation growers had knowledge about soil sterilization practice, digging of trench, use of suitable soil, type of bed preparation, use of planting material, spacing between row and plants, pinching, disbudding, use of support system pest and diseases and harvesting of flowers and treatment of flowers.
- Cent per cent of rose growers adopted recommended practices such as soil sterilization practice, digging of trench, use of suitable soil, type of bed preparation, use of planting material, spacing between row and plants, raking of soil, removal of old leaves, leaves to be retained, removal of suckers and harvesting of flower and treatment of flowers.
- Sixty three per cent of rose growers adopted recommended varieties
- Cent per cent of carnation growers adopted recommended practices such as soil sterilization practice, digging of trench, use of suitable soil, type of bed preparation, use of planting material, spacing between row and plants, pinching, disbudding, use of support system and harvesting of flower and treatment of flowers.
- With respect to FYM application, chemical fertilizer dosage, application of micro and macro nutrients, control measures recommended for pests and diseases and use of preservatives, considerable percentage of farmers were having less knowledge and low adoption of these practices.
- Majority of the respondents (82.81%) belonged to middle age group
- With respect to educational status of the respondents 52% of them were educated up to High School.
- In case of annual income 36% of the respondents belonged to 1000 income category (1 to 10 lakhs)

- Cent per cent of the respondents owned radio and television of which 46.87 per cent had regular television viewing behaviour.
- More number of respondents belonged to high risk orientation category (42.18%) and medium economic motivation category (43.75 %) and high innovativeness category (45.31%).
- Fifty Two per cent of the respondents sold their flowers to local retailers while, Four per cent sold through commission agents.
- Majority 80% of the respondents graded their flowers
- Majority of respondents expressed production problems like limited and irregularity and high investment 20% of power supply (28%).
- Majority expressed the marketing problems like exploitation by the middleman (24%), fluctuation in price (40%) and low price for flowers (28%).
- Cent per cent of the respondents expressed that high profit is the motivational factor to take up cut flower cultivation.

SUGGESTIONS

Implications and Recommendations

In the light of findings of the study and researchers own observations while personally interviewing respondents, following implications are made for effective cut flower cultivation, to the concerned policy makers and cut flowers growers.

Regarding the important cultivation practices of cut flowers, such as FYM application, chemical fertilizer dosage, application of micro and macro nutrients, control measures recommended for pests and diseases and use of preservatives, comparatively farmers were having less knowledge and low adoption of these practices. The information about these practices should be provided from a credible source like the scientists working on cut flower cultivation or the subject matter specialists, who are more knowledgeable about the crop through powerful extension methods like training, field days and conducted tours.

Cut flowers are high value crops and demand more precise information about cultivation practices. So, arrangement should be made to provide printed materials to supplement the information, since most of the cut flower growers are educated and are going to make use of the information to a great extent. This necessitates the need for organizing intensive educational activities such as training, demonstrations, seminars, field days and field visits to successful farms to provide information on technologies not practiced/partially practiced by them.

The demand for good planting material is on the increase. Hence, the production of quality planting material and supply at a reasonable price assumes greater importance.

The absence of organized market emerged as the most important bottleneck in cut flower production. Establishment of an exclusive flower market with required infrastructure to handle the exchange of cut flowers is thus essential. State Government should provide the necessary support in this direction.

The absence of refrigerated infrastructure for transportation and sale of flowers affected the quality of flowers resulting in realizing lower returns by the producers. The provision of cold chain facilities thus assumes great importance. The needed infrastructure for these purposes could be established by forming a viable growers association which in turn could mobilize the needed resources from national Horticulture Board and state Government. Promotion of scientific grading, packing and storage by developing the adequate infrastructural facilities is essential for a sustained growth of the cut flower industry.

CONCLUSION

India has a long floriculture history and flower growing is an age old enterprise. What it has lacked is its commercialization. The growing demands of flowers in the domestic as well as the export

market will require a concerted effort on the part of the government as well as the private entrepreneurs to develop floriculture on scientific lines. Paying attention to the input needs, better resource management and making various policies entrepreneur friendly would lead to a balanced growth of the industry.

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